

Reflexive Year 25: Mathematics of 25 and 2025 in Numbers and Magic Squares

Site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=13652>

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Abstract

*This work brings numerical and magics squares representations for 25 and 2025 in different ways. The number representations are of crazy-type, pyramid-type³, single digit, single letter, running numbers, Triangular, Fibonacci, palindromic-type, prime numbers, embedded prime patterns, repeated digits prime patterns, selfie, semi-selfie, narcissistic, etc. Some interesting patterns for 25 and 2025 are also included in the work. The magic square representations are of there are three types. One is **universal** magic squares with 25 and 2025. By **universal**, we understand that the magic square is **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. In this case, we have constructed magic squares of orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. The second types of magic squares are with **magic sums** 25. In this case, there are only three types of magic squares, i.e., of orders 5, 10 and 25. The third type is magic squares with magic sum 2025. In this case, the magic squares constructed are of orders 3, 5, 6, 9, 10, 15, 18 and 25. In second and third type we have used the **sequential entries** with positive and/or negative numbers.*

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$$25$$

$$1+5+8+8+2+1$$

$$1+2+6+1+9+5+1$$

The above expressions are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, i.e., **universal** summing to 25.

$$96+9|6+1+9|6+96$$

$$1+69+6|9+1+6|9+6|9+96+1$$

$$6+6+69+6|9+6|9+6|9+69+9+9$$

The above three expressions with 1, 6 and 9 are only **upside-down** resulting in sum to 2025.

◀ Reflexive Year 25 ▶

351 2	350 3	343 10	342 11	335 18	334 19	247 106	246 107	255 98	254 99	263 90	262 91
8 345	5 348	16 337	13 340	24 329	21 332	112 241	109 244	104 249	101 252	96 257	93 260
1 352	4 349	9 344	12 341	17 336	20 333	105 248	108 245	97 256	100 253	89 264	92 261
346 7	347 6	338 15	339 14	330 23	331 22	242 111	243 110	250 103	251 102	258 95	259 94
				327 26	326 27	239 114	238 115				
				32 321	29 324	120 233	117 236				
				25 328	28 325	113 240	116 237				
				322 31	323 30	234 119	235 118				
303 50	302 51	311 42	310 43	319 34	318 35	231 122	230 123	223 130	222 131	215 138	214 139
56 297	53 300	48 305	45 308	40 313	37 316	128 225	125 228	136 217	133 220	144 209	141 212
49 304	52 301	41 312	44 309	33 320	36 317	121 232	124 229	129 224	132 221	137 216	140 213
298 55	299 54	306 47	307 46	314 39	315 38	226 127	227 126	218 135	219 134	210 143	211 142
295 58	294 59									207 146	206 147
64 289	61 292									152 201	149 204
57 296	60 293									145 208	148 205
290 63	291 62									202 151	203 150
287 66	286 67	279 74	278 75	271 82	270 83	183 170	182 171	191 162	190 163	199 154	198 155
72 281	69 284	80 273	77 276	88 265	85 268	176 177	173 180	168 185	165 188	160 193	157 196
65 288	68 285	73 280	76 277	81 272	84 269	169 184	172 181	161 192	164 189	153 200	156 197
282 71	283 70	274 79	275 78	266 87	267 86	178 175	179 174	186 167	187 166	194 159	195 158

- *Constructed from 44 stripes (magic rectangles) of equal sums or 22 magic squares of order 4 using sequential entries from 1 to 352.*

7 348 1 350	15 340 9 342	23 332 17 334	111 244 105 246	103 252 97 254	95 260 89 262
2 349 8 347	10 341 16 339	18 333 24 331	106 245 112 243	98 253 104 251	90 261 96 259
352 3 346 5	344 11 338 13	336 19 330 21	248 107 242 109	256 99 250 101	264 91 258 93
345 6 351 4	337 14 343 12	329 22 335 20	241 110 247 108	249 102 255 100	257 94 263 92
		31 324 25 326	119 236 113 238		
		26 325 32 323	114 237 120 235		
		328 27 322 29	240 115 234 117		
		321 30 327 28	233 118 239 116		
55 300 49 302	47 308 41 310	39 316 33 318	127 228 121 230	135 220 129 222	143 212 137 214
50 301 56 299	42 309 48 307	34 317 40 315	122 229 128 227	130 221 136 219	138 213 144 211
304 51 298 53	312 43 306 45	320 35 314 37	232 123 226 125	224 131 218 133	216 139 210 141
297 54 303 52	305 46 311 44	313 38 319 36	225 126 231 124	217 134 223 132	209 142 215 140
63 292 57 294					151 204 145 206
58 293 64 291					146 205 152 203
296 59 290 61					208 147 202 149
289 62 295 60					201 150 207 148
71 284 65 286	79 276 73 278	87 268 81 270	175 180 169 182	167 188 161 190	159 196 153 198
66 285 72 283	74 277 80 275	82 269 88 267	170 181 176 179	162 189 168 187	154 197 160 195
288 67 282 69	280 75 274 77	272 83 266 85	184 171 178 173	192 163 186 165	200 155 194 157
281 70 287 68	273 78 279 76	265 86 271 84	177 174 183 172	185 166 191 164	193 158 199 156

- *Constructed from 22 pandiagonal magic squares of equal sums of order 4 using sequential entries from 1 to 352.*

719 2 718 3 711 10 710 11 703 18 702 19	631 90 630 91 623 98 622 99 615 106 614 107	535 186 534 187 527 194 526 195 519 202 518 203	431 290 430 291 439 282 438 283 447 274 446 275
8 713 5 716 16 705 13 708 24 697 21 700	96 625 93 628 104 617 101 620 112 609 109 612	192 529 189 532 200 521 197 524 208 513 205 516	296 425 293 428 288 433 285 436 280 441 277 444
1 720 4 717 9 712 12 709 17 704 20 701	89 632 92 629 97 624 100 621 105 616 108 613	185 536 188 533 193 528 196 525 201 520 204 517	289 432 292 429 281 440 284 437 273 448 276 445
714 7 715 6 706 15 707 14 698 23 699 22	626 95 627 94 618 103 619 102 610 111 611 110	530 191 531 190 522 199 523 198 514 207 515 206	426 295 427 294 434 287 435 286 442 279 443 278
	695 26 694 27		423 298 422 299
	32 689 29 692		304 417 301 420
	25 696 28 693		297 424 300 421
	690 31 691 30		418 303 419 302
671 50 670 51 679 42 678 43 687 34 686 35	551 170 550 171	599 122 598 123	415 306 414 307 407 314 406 315 399 322 398 323
56 665 53 668 48 673 45 676 40 681 37 684	176 545 173 548	128 593 125 596	312 409 309 412 320 401 317 404 328 393 325 396
49 672 52 669 41 680 44 677 33 688 36 685	169 552 172 549	121 600 124 597	305 416 308 413 313 408 316 405 321 400 324 397
666 55 667 54 674 47 675 46 682 39 683 38	546 175 547 174	594 127 595 126	410 311 411 310 402 319 403 318 394 327 395 326
663 58 662 59	559 162 558 163	591 130 590 131	
64 657 61 660	168 553 165 556	136 585 133 588	391 330 390 331
57 664 60 661	161 560 164 557	129 592 132 589	336 385 333 388
658 63 659 62	554 167 555 166	586 135 587 134	329 392 332 389
			386 335 387 334
655 66 654 67 647 74 646 75 639 82 638 83	567 154 566 155 575 146 574 147 583 138 582 139	471 250 470 251 463 258 462 259 455 266 454 267	367 354 366 355 375 346 374 347 383 338 382 339
72 649 69 652 80 641 77 644 88 633 85 636	160 561 157 564 152 569 149 572 144 577 141 580	256 465 253 468 264 457 261 460 272 449 269 452	360 361 357 364 352 369 349 372 344 377 341 380
65 656 68 653 73 648 76 645 81 640 84 637	153 568 156 565 145 576 148 573 137 584 140 581	249 472 252 469 257 464 260 461 265 456 268 453	353 368 356 365 345 376 348 373 337 384 340 381
650 71 651 70 642 79 643 78 634 87 635 86	562 159 563 158 570 151 571 150 578 143 579 142	466 255 467 254 458 263 459 262 450 271 451 270	362 359 363 358 370 351 371 350 378 343 379 342

- *Constructed from 90 stripes (magic rectangles) of equal sums or 45 magic squares of order 4 using sequential entries from 1 to 720.*

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1 Crazy Representations

Below are representations of 25 and 2025 in terms of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1.

1.1 Basic Operations

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2025 &:= 12 \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ &:= 9 \times 8 + 76 + 5^4 \times 3 + 2 \times 1\end{aligned}$$

1.1.1 10 numbers 1, 2,... 10: Increasing and Decreasing

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 \\ &:= 10 + 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2025 &:= 12 \times 3 + 45 \times 6 \times 7 + 89 + 10 \\ &:= 10 + (9 + 8 \times 76 + 54) \times 3 + 2 \times 1\end{aligned}$$

1.2 Factorial/Square-Root

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 1 \times 2^{3!} - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + \sqrt{43 + 21}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2025 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)\end{aligned}$$

1.3 Square Function

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= Q(1 \times 2^3) - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ &:= -9 + Q(8 - 7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= Q(-1 - 2 + Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ &:= Q(Q(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

1.4 Cubic Function

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= C(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= -1 + 2 \times (C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ &:= -9 + C(8 + 7) - C(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

1.5 Fibonacci Sequence

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 1 + 2 - F(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ &:= 9 + 8 - F(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3^{F(4)} \times (-5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ &:= -9 \times 8 + F(F(7)) \times (-6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

1.6 Triangular Numbers

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 1 - T(2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ &:= -9 + T(8) + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= T(-1 + T(2 + 3 + 4)) + T(T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ &:= -9 - T(8 \times 7) + T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

2 Pyramid-Type Representations

Below are **pyramid-type** representations of 25 and 2025, where there is a permutation of bases and powers. It is understood that $0^a = 0$, $a \neq 1$, $0^0 = 1$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{25} &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 \\
 &:= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 \\
 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^0 \\
 &:= 1^4 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^2 \\
 &:= 0^4 + 1^0 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^2 \\
 &:= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^1 \\
 &:= -1^8 - 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
 &:= 0^3 + 1^5 + 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 6^2 \\
 &:= 1^9 + 2^6 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 \\
 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 + 2^7 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^3 \\
 &:= 0^6 - 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
 &:= -1^5 + 2^9 - 3^8 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
 &:= 0^6 + 1^9 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 9^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2025} &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 \\
 &:= 0^2 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 \\
 &:= 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
 &:= -1^8 + 2^5 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
 &:= 0^3 - 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 6^4 \\
 &:= 1^7 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
 &:= 0^4 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
 &:= 0^5 + 1^7 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
 &:= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^8 - 4^9 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 8^6 + 9^1 \\
 &:= 0^7 - 1^9 + 2^6 - 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 9^0
 \end{aligned}$$

2.1 Patterns in Power and Base Permutables for 25

(i)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{25\ 0} &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 1} &:= 0^3 - 1^8 + 2^6 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^0 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 2} &:= 0^7 - 1^0 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 3} &:= 0^3 + 1^8 + 2^6 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^0 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 4} &:= 0^7 + 1^0 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 5} &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 6} &:= 0^3 + 1^8 + 2^6 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 7} &:= 0^7 - 1^8 + 2^6 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 8^0 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 8} &:= 0^5 - 1^0 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 \mathbf{25\ 9} &:= 0^7 + 1^8 + 2^6 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 8^0
 \end{aligned}$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned}1\ 25 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\2\ 25 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 \\3\ 25 &:= 0^6 + 1^8 + 2^7 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\4\ 25 &:= 0^6 + 1^7 - 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 8^0 \\5\ 25 &:= 0^5 + 1^8 + 2^6 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 \\6\ 25 &:= 0^7 + 1^8 - 2^5 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\7\ 25 &:= 0^4 + 1^7 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 8^0 \\8\ 25 &:= 0^6 + 1^8 + 2^7 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\9\ 25 &:= 0^6 + 1^7 + 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 8^0\end{aligned}$$

(iii)

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 0^6 + 1^9 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\250 &:= 0^6 + 1^8 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 9^1 \\2500 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 + 8^2 + 9^1 \\25000 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\250000 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 7^6 + 8^5 + 9^3\end{aligned}$$

(iv)

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 0^6 + 1^9 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\255 &:= 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 9^0 \\2555 &:= 0^8 - 1^9 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\25555 &:= 0^5 + 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\255555 &:= 0^2 + 1^8 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 8^6 + 9^0\end{aligned}$$

2.2 Patterns in Power and Base Permutables for 2025

(i)

$$\begin{aligned}
 2025\ 0 &:= 0^3 - 1^8 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
 2025\ 1 &:= 0^3 + 1^8 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 2025\ 2 &:= 0^3 + 1^8 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
 2025\ 3 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
 2025\ 4 &:= 0^4 - 1^0 - 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
 2025\ 5 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
 2025\ 6 &:= 0^4 + 1^0 - 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
 2025\ 7 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
 2025\ 8 &:= 0^6 - 1^0 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
 2025\ 9 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^2
 \end{aligned}$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned}
 1\ 2025 &:= 0^2 + 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 \\
 2\ 2025 &:= 0^5 + 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 8^4 \\
 3\ 2025 &:= 0^6 - 1^8 + 2^0 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^5 \\
 4\ 2025 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 8^5 \\
 5\ 2025 &:= 0^2 + 1^8 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 8^0 \\
 6\ 2025 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
 7\ 2025 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 8^4 \\
 8\ 2025 &:= 0^2 - 1^6 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 \\
 9\ 2025 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 8^5
 \end{aligned}$$

(iii)

$$\begin{aligned}
 2025 &:= 0^7 - 1^9 + 2^6 - 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 9^0 \\
 20250 &:= 0^6 + 1^9 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
 202500 &:= 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 7^6 + 8^2 + 9^4
 \end{aligned}$$

(iv)

$$\begin{aligned}
 2025 &:= 0^7 - 1^9 + 2^6 - 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 9^0 \\
 20255 &:= 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 8^3 + 9^2 \\
 202555 &:= 0^4 + 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^8 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 8^6 + 9^1
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Single Digit Representations

Below are **single digit** representations of 25 and 2025 in terms of 1 to 9 separately:

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \\ &:= 2 + 22 + 2/2 \\ &:= 3^3 - 3 + 3/3 \\ &:= 4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \\ &:= 6 \times 6 - 66/6 \\ &:= 7 + 7 + 77/7 \\ &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8 \\ &:= 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= (1 + 1)^{11} - 11 - 11 - 1 \\ &:= (2 \times 22 + 2/2)^2 \\ &:= 3 \times (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 + 3^3) \\ &:= (44 + 4/4)^{(4+4)/4} \\ &:= 5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5) \\ &:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 \times 6 + ((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6))^6 \\ &:= (7 + 7 + 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7) \\ &:= 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8) + 8/8 \\ &:= 9 \times ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 99) \end{aligned}$$

4 Pattern in Single Digit

4.1 Pattern in Single Digit for 25

1.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \\ 225 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\ 2225 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1111) \\ 22225 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11111) \end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \\ 235 &:= 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\ 2335 &:= 111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1111) \\ 23335 &:= 1111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11111) \end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \\ 245 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 111) \\ 2445 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (111 + 1111) \\ 24445 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1111 + 11111) \end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \\ 255 &:= 11 + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 111) \\ 2555 &:= 111 + (1 + 1) \times (111 + 1111) \\ 25555 &:= 1111 + (1 + 1) \times (1111 + 11111) \end{aligned}$$

5.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 2 + 22 + 2/2 \\225 &:= 2 + 222 + 2/2 \\2225 &:= 2 + 2222 + 2/2 \\22225 &:= 2 + 22222 + 2/2\end{aligned}$$

6.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 2 + 22 + 2/2 \\235 &:= 2 + 222 + 22/2 \\2335 &:= 2 + 2222 + 222/2 \\23335 &:= 2 + 22222 + 2222/2\end{aligned}$$

7.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 2 + 22 + 2/2 \\245 &:= 22 + 222 + 2/2 \\2445 &:= 222 + 2222 + 2/2 \\24445 &:= 2222 + 22222 + 2/2\end{aligned}$$

8.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 2 + 22 + 2/2 \\255 &:= 22 + 222 + 22/2 \\2555 &:= 222 + 2222 + 222/2 \\25555 &:= 2222 + 22222 + 2222/2\end{aligned}$$

9.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4 \\235 &:= 4 + 44 + 44 \times 4 + 44/4 \\2335 &:= 4 + 444 + 444 \times 4 + 444/4 \\23335 &:= 4 + 4444 + 4444 \times 4 + 4444/4\end{aligned}$$

10.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4 \\265 &:= 44 + 44 + 44 \times 4 + 4/4 \\2665 &:= 444 + 444 + 444 \times 4 + 4/4 \\26665 &:= 4444 + 4444 + 4444 \times 4 + 4/4\end{aligned}$$

11.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4 \\275 &:= 44 + 44 + 44 \times 4 + 44/4 \\2775 &:= 444 + 444 + 444 \times 4 + 444/4 \\27775 &:= 4444 + 4444 + 4444 \times 4 + 4444/4\end{aligned}$$

12.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 5 \times 5 \\3025 &:= 55 \times 55 \\308025 &:= 555 \times 555 \\30858025 &:= 5555 \times 5555\end{aligned}$$

13.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 6 \times 6 - 66/6 \\285 &:= 66 \times 6 - 666/6 \\2885 &:= 666 \times 6 - 6666/6 \\28885 &:= 6666 \times 6 - 66666/6\end{aligned}$$

14.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 6 \times 6 - 66/6 \\4245 &:= 66 \times 66 - 666/6 \\442445 &:= 666 \times 666 - 6666/6 \\44424445 &:= 6666 \times 6666 - 66666/6\end{aligned}$$

15.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 7 + 7 + 77/7 \\265 &:= 77 + 77 + 777/7 \\2665 &:= 777 + 777 + 7777/7 \\26665 &:= 7777 + 7777 + 77777/7\end{aligned}$$

16.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8 \\265 &:= 88 + 88 + 88 + 8/8 \\2665 &:= 888 + 888 + 888 + 8/8 \\26665 &:= 8888 + 8888 + 8888 + 8/8\end{aligned}$$

17.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8 \\275 &:= 88 + 88 + 88 + 88/8 \\2775 &:= 888 + 888 + 888 + 888/8 \\27775 &:= 8888 + 8888 + 8888 + 8888/8\end{aligned}$$

18.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9 \\205 &:= 99 + 99 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9 \\2005 &:= 999 + 999 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9 \\20005 &:= 9999 + 9999 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9\end{aligned}$$

19.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9 \\295 &:= 99 + 99 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9 \\2995 &:= 999 + 999 + 999 - (9 + 9)/9 \\29995 &:= 9999 + 9999 + 9999 - (9 + 9)/9\end{aligned}$$

20.

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9 \\275 &:= 99 + 99 + 99 - (99 + 99)/9 \\2775 &:= 999 + 999 + 999 - (999 + 999)/9 \\27775 &:= 9999 + 9999 + 9999 - (9999 + 9999)/9\end{aligned}$$

4.2 Pattern in Single Digit for 2025

1.

$$\begin{aligned}2025 &:= 5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5) \\22025 &:= 5 \times (55 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5) \\222025 &:= 5 \times (555 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5) \\2222025 &:= 5 \times (5555 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5)\end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}2025 &:= (7 + 7 + 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7) \\20925 &:= (77 + 77 + 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7) \\209925 &:= (777 + 777 + 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7) \\2099925 &:= (7777 + 7777 + 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)\end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned}2025 &:= 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8) + 8/8 \\20425 &:= 888 \times (8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8) + 8/8 \\204425 &:= 8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8) + 8/8 \\2044425 &:= 88888 \times (8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8) + 8/8\end{aligned}$$

5 Single Letter Representations

$$25 := \frac{aa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$2025 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

where, $aaaaa = a10^4 + a10^3 + a10^2 + a10 + a,$

$$aaaa = a10^3 + a10^2 + a10 + a,$$

$$aaa = a10^2 + a10 + a,$$

$$aa = a10 + a, \text{ etc.}$$

$$a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}.$$

5.1 Patterns in Single Letter for 25

1.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= \frac{aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 125 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1125 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11125 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= \frac{aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 225 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 2225 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 22225 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= \frac{aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 245 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + aa + a}{a} \\ 2445 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaa + aaa + a}{a} \\ 24445 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa + aaaa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= \frac{aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 235 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 2335 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 23335 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

5.

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= \frac{aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 255 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + aa + aa}{a} \\ 2555 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa}{a} \\ 25555 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa + aaaa + aaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

5.2 Patterns in Single Letter for 2025

1.

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 22025 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 222025 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2222025 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 20025 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 200025 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2000025 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa - aaaaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 20225 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 202225 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa + aaaa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2022225 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa - aaaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 20245 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 202445 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa + aaaa + aaa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2024445 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa - aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

5.

$$\begin{aligned}
 2025 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 20045 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 200245 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa + aa + aaa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 2002245 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa - aaaaaa + aa + aaaa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

6 Running Equalities for 25 and 2025

6.1 Running Equalities for 25

$$\begin{aligned}
 25 &:= 1 + (-2 + 3)! &= 4 \times 5 - 67 + 8 \times 9 \\
 & &= \sqrt{4} \times 56 - 78 - 9 \\
 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 \\
 &:= 1 \times 23 + \sqrt{4} &= 56/7 + 8 + 9 \\
 &:= 1 + 23 - 4 + 5 \\
 &:= (123 + \sqrt{4})/5 &= (67 + 8)/\sqrt{9} \\
 & &= 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \\
 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 - 6 &= 5 - 4 + 3 + 21 \\
 &:= \sqrt{9} + 87 - 65 \\
 &:= 98/7 + 6 + 5 &= 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 & &= 4! - 3^2 + 10 \\
 &:= (9 + 87)/6 + 5 + 4 &= (3! - 2)! + 1 \\
 & &= 3 + 21 + 0!
 \end{aligned}$$

6.2 Running Equality for 2025

$$2025 := 9 - 8!/7 + 6^5 = (43 + 2)^{1+0!}$$

7 Pythagorean Triples

$$\begin{array}{ll} 156^2 + 2025^2 := 2031^2 & 2025^2 + 9000^2 := 9225^2 \\ 1080^2 + 2025^2 := 2295^2 & 2025^2 + 15120^2 := 15255^2 \\ 1260^2 + 2025^2 := 2385^2 & 2025^2 + 16340^2 := 16465^2 \\ 2025^2 + 2448^2 := 3177^2 & 2025^2 + 25272^2 := 25353^2 \\ 2025^2 + 2700^2 := 3375^2 & 2025^2 + 27300^2 := 27375^2 \\ 2025^2 + 2968^2 := 3593^2 & 2025^2 + 45540^2 := 45585^2 \\ 2025^2 + 4860^2 := 5265^2 & 2025^2 + 75924^2 := 75951^2 \\ 2025^2 + 5280^2 := 5655^2 & 2025^2 + 82000^2 := 82025^2 \\ 2025^2 + 8316^2 := 8559^2 & 2025^2 + 136680^2 := 136695^2 \end{array}$$

7.1 Pattern in Pythagorean Triples with 25

1.

$$\begin{array}{ll} 24^2 + 7^2 & := 25^2 \\ 2244^2 + 67^2 & := 2245^2 \\ 222444^2 + 667^2 & := 222445^2 \\ 22224444^2 + 6667^2 & := 22224445^2 \end{array}$$

2.

$$\begin{array}{ll} 20^2 + 15^2 & := 25^2 \\ 2720^2 + 165^2 & := 2725^2 \\ 277220^2 + 1665^2 & := 277225^2 \\ 27772220^2 + 16665^2 & := 27772225^2 \end{array}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned}24^2 + 7^2 &:= 25^2 \\2664^2 + 73^2 &:= 2665^2 \\226464^2 + 673^2 &:= 226465^2 \\22264464^2 + 6673^2 &:= 22264465^2\end{aligned}$$

7.2 Pattern in Pythagorean Triples with 2025

1.

$$\begin{aligned}18042024^2 + 6007^2 &:= 18042025^2 \\1800420024^2 + 60007^2 &:= 1800420025^2 \\180004200024^2 + 600007^2 &:= 180004200025^2 \\18000042000024^2 + 6000007^2 &:= 18000042000025^2\end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}7975^2 + 9000^2 &:= 12025^2 \\102007975^2 + 909000^2 &:= 102012025^2 \\1020302007975^2 + 90909000^2 &:= 1020302012025^2 \\10203040302007975^2 + 9090909000^2 &:= 10203040302012025^2\end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned}997975^2 + 90000^2 &:= 1002025^2 \\10200997975^2 + 9090000^2 &:= 10201002025^2 \\102030200997975^2 + 909090000^2 &:= 102030201002025^2 \\1020304030200997975^2 + 90909090000^2 &:= 1020304030201002025^2\end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned}957975^2 + 410000^2 &:= 1042025^2 \\10200957975^2 + 41410000^2 &:= 10201042025^2 \\102030200957975^2 + 4141410000^2 &:= 102030201042025^2 \\1020304030200957975^2 + 414141410000^2 &:= 1020304030201042025^2\end{aligned}$$

5.

$$\begin{aligned}797500^2 + 900000^2 &:= 1202500^2 \\10200797500^2 + 90900000^2 &:= 10201202500^2 \\102030200797500^2 + 9090900000^2 &:= 102030201202500^2 \\1020304030200797500^2 + 909090900000^2 &:= 1020304030201202500^2\end{aligned}$$

6.

$$\begin{aligned}367975^2 + 1590000^2 &:= 1632025^2 \\10200367975^2 + 160590000^2 &:= 10201632025^2 \\102030200367975^2 + 16060590000^2 &:= 102030201632025^2 \\1020304030200367975^2 + 1606060590000^2 &:= 1020304030201632025^2\end{aligned}$$

7.

$$\begin{aligned}87975^2 + 1910000^2 &:= 1912025^2 \\10200087975^2 + 192910000^2 &:= 10201912025^2 \\102030200087975^2 + 19292910000^2 &:= 102030201912025^2 \\1020304030200087975^2 + 1929292910000^2 &:= 1020304030201912025^2\end{aligned}$$

8.

$$\begin{aligned}202551^2 + 1786000^2 &:= 1797449^2 \\10200202551^2 + 180386000^2 &:= 10201797449^2 \\102030200202551^2 + 18040386000^2 &:= 102030201797449^2 \\1020304030200202551^2 + 1804040386000^2 &:= 1020304030201797449^2\end{aligned}$$

8 Selfie Representations for 25 and 2025

8.1 Reverse Way

$$\begin{aligned}25 &:= 5^2 \\2502 &:= 2 + 50^2\end{aligned}$$

8.2 Fibonacci, Triangular and Quadratic Functions

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= T(F(T(T(2))) + 0!)^{F(-2+5)} \\ 2025 &:= (T(5) \times T(2))^{02} \\ 2025 &:= Q(20 + 25) \end{aligned}$$

where, T, F and Q are **Triangular**, **Fibonacci** and **Quadratic** functions.

8.3 Pattern with 25

(i)

$$\begin{aligned} 20 \times 100 + 25 &= 2025 := Q(20 + 25) \\ 21 \times 100 + 25 &= 2125 := (Q(2) + Q(Q(1 + 2))) \times Q(5) \\ 22 \times 100 + 25 &= 2225 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(-2 + Q(2 + 5)) \\ 23 \times 100 + 25 &= 2325 := (Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(3//))) - Q(2) \times Q(5) \\ 24 \times 100 + 25 &= 2425 := 24 + Q(Q(2 + 5)) \\ 25 \times 100 + 25 &= 2525 := Q(25 \times 2) + Q(5) \\ 26 \times 100 + 25 &= 2625 := (Q(2) + Q(Q(6))) \times 2 + Q(5) \\ 27 \times 100 + 25 &= 2725 := (Q(Q(2)) + Q(7 + Q(Q(2)))) \times 5 \\ 28 \times 100 + 25 &= 2825 := Q(Q(2)) + Q(Q(8) - Q(Q(2)) + 5) \\ 29 \times 100 + 25 &= 2925 := (Q(2 + 9) - Q(2)) \times Q(5) \\ 30 \times 100 + 25 &= 3025 := Q(30 + 25) \end{aligned}$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned} 25 \times 10 + 0 &= 250 := 2 \times C(5) + 0 \\ 25 \times 10 + 1 &= 251 := 2 \times C(5) + 1 \\ 25 \times 10 + 2 &= 252 := 2 \times C(5) + 2 \\ 25 \times 10 + 3 &= 253 := 2 \times C(5) + 3 \\ 25 \times 10 + 4 &= 254 := 2 \times C(5) + 4 \\ 25 \times 10 + 5 &= 255 := 2 \times C(5) + 5 \\ 25 \times 10 + 6 &= 256 := 2 \times C(5) + 6 \\ 25 \times 10 + 7 &= 257 := 2 \times C(5) + 7 \\ 25 \times 10 + 8 &= 258 := 2 \times C(5) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$25 \times 10 + 9 = \mathbf{259} := 2 \times C(5) + 9$$

(iii)

$$\begin{aligned} 25 \times 1000 + 920 &= \mathbf{25920} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 921 &= \mathbf{25921} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 922 &= \mathbf{25922} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 923 &= \mathbf{25923} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 924 &= \mathbf{25924} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 925 &= \mathbf{25925} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 926 &= \mathbf{25926} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 927 &= \mathbf{25927} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 928 &= \mathbf{25928} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8 \\ 25 \times 1000 + 929 &= \mathbf{25929} := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9. \end{aligned}$$

9 Selfie Fractions for 25 and 2025

9.1 Selfie Fractions for 25

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{250}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{2 \times 50} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{375}} &:= \frac{2 + 5}{3 \times 7 \times 5} \\ \frac{\mathbf{1295}}{\mathbf{25}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{1 + 2^9 + 5} \\ \frac{\mathbf{1835}}{\mathbf{25}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{(1 + 8)^3 + 5} \\ \frac{\mathbf{2435}}{\mathbf{25}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{2 + 4 \times 3^5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{2500}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{2 \times 500} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{3240}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{(3 \times 2)^{4+0}} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{3375}} &:= \frac{2 + 5}{3^3 \times 7 \times 5} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{3750}} &:= \frac{2 + 5}{3 \times (7 \times 50)} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{6075}} &:= \frac{2^5}{6^{0 \times 7 + 5}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{10875}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{10 \times 87 \times 5} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{14650}} &:= \frac{2 + 5}{1 + ((4^6) + (5 + 0))} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{14675}} &:= \frac{2 + 5}{1 + 4^6 + 7 + 5} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{16075}} &:= \frac{2 + 5}{1 + 60 \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

9.2 Patterns in Selfie Fractions for 25

1.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{165}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{1 + 65} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{1665}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{1 + 665} \\ \frac{\mathbf{25}}{\mathbf{16665}} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{1 + 6665} \end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{25}{275} &:= \frac{2+5}{2+75} \\ \frac{25}{2775} &:= \frac{2+5}{2+775} \\ \frac{25}{27775} &:= \frac{2+5}{2+7775} \\ \frac{25}{277775} &:= \frac{2+5}{2+77775} \end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{25}{375} &:= \frac{2+5}{3 \times 7 \times 5} \\ \frac{25}{3750} &:= \frac{2+5}{3 \times 7 \times 50} \\ \frac{25}{37500} &:= \frac{2+5}{3 \times 7 \times 500} \\ \frac{25}{375000} &:= \frac{2+5}{3 \times 7 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{25}{3375} &:= \frac{2+5}{3^3 \times 7 \times 5} \\ \frac{25}{33750} &:= \frac{2+5}{3^3 \times 7 \times 50} \\ \frac{25}{337500} &:= \frac{2+5}{3^3 \times 7 \times 500} \\ \frac{25}{3375000} &:= \frac{2+5}{3^3 \times 7 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

5.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{25}{10875} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{10 \times 87 \times 5} \\ \frac{25}{108750} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{10 \times 87 \times 50} \\ \frac{25}{1087500} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{10 \times 87 \times 500} \\ \frac{25}{10875000} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{10 \times 87 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

9.3 Selfie Fractions for 2025

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{10125} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 \times 2 + 5)}{(1 + 01) \times 25} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 02 \times 5}{10 \times 1 \times 2 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 025}{10 \times 1 \times 25} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 02 \times 5}{1 \times 01 \times 2 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{10125} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 25}{1 \times 01 \times 2 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{20 + 2 \times 5}{10 \times (1 + 2) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 02^5}{10 \times 1 \times 2^5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (02 + 5)}{10 \times 1 \times (2 + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{10125} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 2 + 5}{10 \times 1 + 25} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 02^5}{10 \times (12 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 025}{10 + 125} \\ &:= \frac{20 + 2^5}{10 \times (1 + 25)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{18225} &:= \frac{2 \times 0 \times 2 + 5}{18 + 2 + 25} \\ &:= \frac{2^{02 \times 5}}{(1 + 8) \times 2^{2 \times 5}} \\ &:= \frac{(20 + 2) \times 5}{(1 + 8) \times 22 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(20 + 2)^5}{(1 + 8) \times 22^5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 \times 2 + 5)}{1 + 82 + 2 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 02 \times 5}{(1 + 8) \times 2 \times 2 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{18225} &:= \frac{2 \times 02^5}{(1 + 8) \times 2 \times 2^5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (02 + 5)}{(1 + 8 + 2)^2 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 025}{(1 + 8) \times 2 \times 25} \\ &:= \frac{2^{(02 + 5)}}{18 \times 2 \times 2^5} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 02 \times 5}{1 + 82 + 25} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{18225} &:= \frac{2 + 02^5}{(1 + 8) \times (2 + 2^5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 02 + 5}{(1 + 8) \times (2 + 2 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 25}{1 + 8 + 2 + 2 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 025}{18 + 225} \\ &:= \frac{20 \times 2 \times 5}{1 \times 8 \times 225} \\ &:= \frac{20 + 25}{(18 + 2)^2 + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{45}{2025} &:= \frac{4 + 5}{20^2 + 5} \\ \frac{81}{2025} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{20 \times 2 \times 5} \\ \frac{125}{2025} &:= \frac{1 \times 25}{(20^2) + 5} \\ \frac{175}{2025} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{(20^2) + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{2025} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times 3)}{20 \times 2 \times 5} \\ \frac{405}{2025} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 5}{2 \times 02 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 05}{20 + 25} \\ \frac{495}{2025} &:= \frac{4 + 95}{20^2 + 5} \\ \frac{729}{2025} &:= \frac{7 + 2 + 9}{2 \times 025} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{810}{2025} &:= \frac{8 \times 1 + 0}{2 \times (0 + (2 \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 10}{20 + 25} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 10}{20 \times 2 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

9.4 Patterns in Selfie Fractions for 2025

1.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{81}{2025} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{20 \times 2 \times 5} \\ \frac{481}{12025} &:= \frac{48 \times 1}{120 \times 2 \times 5} \\ \frac{4481}{112025} &:= \frac{448 \times 1}{1120 \times 2 \times 5} \\ \frac{44481}{1112025} &:= \frac{4448 \times 1}{11120 \times 2 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{11475} &:= \frac{20 + 25}{(11 \times 4 + 7) \times 5} \\ \frac{2025}{114750} &:= \frac{20 + 25}{(11 \times 4 + 7) \times 50} \\ \frac{2025}{1147500} &:= \frac{20 + 25}{(11 \times 4 + 7) \times 500} \\ \frac{2025}{11475000} &:= \frac{20 + 25}{(11 \times 4 + 7) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{10125} &:= \frac{2 \times 0 \times 2 + 5}{1 \times 01 \times 25} \\ \frac{2025}{101250} &:= \frac{2 \times 0 \times 2 + 5}{1 \times 01 \times 250} \\ \frac{2025}{1012500} &:= \frac{2 \times 0 \times 2 + 5}{1 \times 01 \times 2500} \\ \frac{2025}{10125000} &:= \frac{2 \times 0 \times 2 + 5}{1 \times 01 \times 25000} \end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2025}{14175} &:= \frac{2 \times 2 \times 5}{(1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 7 \times 5)} \\ \frac{2025}{141750} &:= \frac{2 \times 2 \times 5}{(1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 7 \times 50)} \\ \frac{2025}{1417500} &:= \frac{2 \times 2 \times 5}{(1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 7 \times 500)} \\ \frac{2025}{14175000} &:= \frac{2 \times 2 \times 5}{(1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 7 \times 5000)} \end{aligned}$$

10 Equivalent Fractions

$\frac{25}{13460} := \frac{40}{21536}$	$\frac{25}{1067438} := \frac{50}{2134876}$	$\frac{25}{1074368} := \frac{50}{2148736}$
$\frac{25}{138746} := \frac{75}{416238}$	$\frac{25}{1068374} := \frac{50}{2136748}$	$\frac{25}{1083674} := \frac{50}{2167348}$
$\frac{25}{143876} := \frac{75}{431628}$	$\frac{25}{1068437} := \frac{50}{2136874}$	$\frac{25}{1084367} := \frac{50}{2168734}$
$\frac{25}{1034876} := \frac{75}{3104628}$	$\frac{25}{1068734} := \frac{50}{2137468}$	$\frac{25}{1086734} := \frac{50}{2173468}$
$\frac{25}{1048736} := \frac{50}{3146208}$	$\frac{25}{1068743} := \frac{50}{2137486}$	$\frac{25}{1086743} := \frac{50}{2173486}$
$\frac{25}{1067384} := \frac{50}{2134768}$	$\frac{25}{1073684} := \frac{50}{2147368}$	$\frac{25}{1306874} := \frac{50}{2613748}$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{1308674} := \frac{50}{2617348} \\ \frac{25}{1340687} := \frac{50}{2681374} \\ \frac{25}{1340867} := \frac{75}{2681734} \\ \frac{25}{1346087} := \frac{80}{4038261} \\ \frac{25}{1347680} := \frac{50}{4312576} \\ \frac{25}{1367084} := \frac{50}{2734168} \\ \frac{25}{1367408} := \frac{50}{2734816} \\ \frac{25}{1368074} := \frac{50}{2736148} \\ \frac{25}{1368407} := \frac{50}{2736814} \\ \frac{25}{1370684} := \frac{50}{2741368} \\ \frac{25}{1374068} := \frac{75}{2748136} \\ \frac{25}{1378964} := \frac{50}{4136892} \\ \frac{25}{1380674} := \frac{50}{2761348} \\ \frac{25}{1384067} := \frac{75}{2768134} \\ \frac{25}{1387460} := \frac{75}{4162380} \\ \frac{25}{1387964} := \frac{75}{4163892} \\ \frac{25}{1389746} := \frac{75}{4169238} \\ \frac{25}{1398746} := \frac{50}{4196238} \\ \frac{25}{1406738} := \frac{50}{2813476} \\ \frac{25}{1406837} := \frac{50}{2813674} \\ \frac{25}{1406873} := \frac{50}{2813746} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{1407368} := \frac{50}{2814736} \\ \frac{25}{1408367} := \frac{50}{2816734} \\ \frac{25}{1408673} := \frac{50}{2817346} \\ \frac{25}{1430687} := \frac{50}{2861374} \\ \frac{25}{1430867} := \frac{75}{2861734} \\ \frac{25}{1436087} := \frac{50}{4308261} \\ \frac{25}{1436708} := \frac{50}{2873416} \\ \frac{25}{1436807} := \frac{50}{2873614} \\ \frac{25}{1437068} := \frac{50}{2874136} \\ \frac{25}{1438067} := \frac{75}{2876134} \\ \frac{25}{1438760} := \frac{75}{4316280} \\ \frac{25}{1438976} := \frac{75}{4316928} \\ \frac{25}{1439876} := \frac{40}{4319628} \\ \frac{25}{1473860} := \frac{80}{2358176} \\ \quad := \frac{60}{4716352} \\ \frac{25}{1478630} := \frac{50}{3548712} \\ \frac{25}{1607384} := \frac{50}{3214768} \\ \frac{25}{1607438} := \frac{50}{3214876} \\ \frac{25}{1608374} := \frac{50}{3216748} \\ \frac{25}{1608437} := \frac{50}{3216874} \\ \frac{25}{1608734} := \frac{50}{3217468} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{1608743} := \frac{50}{3217486} \\ \frac{25}{1630874} := \frac{50}{3261748} \\ \frac{25}{1634087} := \frac{50}{3268174} \\ \frac{25}{1637084} := \frac{50}{3274168} \\ \frac{25}{1637408} := \frac{75}{3274816} \\ \frac{25}{1637894} := \frac{50}{4913682} \\ \frac{25}{1638074} := \frac{50}{3276148} \\ \frac{25}{1638407} := \frac{75}{3276814} \\ \frac{25}{1638794} := \frac{50}{4916382} \\ \frac{25}{1640738} := \frac{50}{3281476} \\ \frac{25}{1640837} := \frac{50}{3281674} \\ \frac{25}{1640873} := \frac{50}{3281746} \\ \frac{25}{1643087} := \frac{50}{3286174} \\ \frac{25}{1643708} := \frac{50}{3287416} \\ \frac{25}{1643807} := \frac{50}{3287614} \\ \frac{25}{1706384} := \frac{50}{3412768} \\ \frac{25}{1706438} := \frac{50}{3412876} \\ \frac{25}{1708364} := \frac{50}{3416728} \\ \frac{25}{1708436} := \frac{50}{3416872} \\ \frac{25}{1708634} := \frac{50}{3417268} \\ \frac{25}{1708643} := \frac{50}{3417286} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{1730864} := \frac{50}{3461728} \\ \frac{25}{1734086} := \frac{50}{3468172} \\ \frac{25}{1736084} := \frac{50}{3472168} \\ \frac{25}{1736408} := \frac{70}{3472816} \\ \frac{25}{1736840} := \frac{50}{4863152} \\ \frac{25}{1738064} := \frac{50}{3476128} \\ \frac{25}{1738406} := \frac{40}{3476812} \\ \frac{25}{1738460} := \frac{50}{2781536} \\ \frac{25}{1740638} := \frac{50}{3481276} \\ \frac{25}{1740836} := \frac{50}{3481672} \\ \frac{25}{1740863} := \frac{50}{3481726} \\ \frac{25}{1743086} := \frac{50}{3486172} \\ \frac{25}{1743608} := \frac{50}{3487216} \\ \frac{25}{1743806} := \frac{50}{3487612} \\ \frac{25}{1806374} := \frac{50}{3612748} \\ \frac{25}{1806437} := \frac{50}{3612874} \\ \frac{25}{1807364} := \frac{50}{3614728} \\ \frac{25}{1807436} := \frac{50}{3614872} \\ \frac{25}{1836074} := \frac{50}{3672148} \\ \frac{25}{1836407} := \frac{50}{3672814} \\ \frac{25}{1837064} := \frac{50}{3674128} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{1837406} := \frac{50}{3674812} \\ \frac{25}{1840637} := \frac{50}{3681274} \\ \frac{25}{1840736} := \frac{50}{3681472} \\ \frac{25}{1843607} := \frac{50}{3687214} \\ \frac{25}{1843706} := \frac{50}{3687412} \\ \frac{25}{1860734} := \frac{50}{3721468} \\ \frac{25}{1860743} := \frac{50}{3721486} \\ \frac{25}{1863074} := \frac{50}{3726148} \\ \frac{25}{1863407} := \frac{50}{3726814} \\ \frac{25}{1864073} := \frac{50}{3728146} \\ \frac{25}{1864307} := \frac{50}{3728614} \\ \frac{25}{1870634} := \frac{50}{3741268} \\ \frac{25}{1870643} := \frac{50}{3741286} \\ \frac{25}{1873064} := \frac{50}{3746128} \\ \frac{25}{1873406} := \frac{50}{3746812} \\ \frac{25}{1874063} := \frac{50}{3748126} \\ \frac{25}{1874306} := \frac{50}{3748612} \\ \frac{25}{3061874} := \frac{50}{6123748} \\ \frac{25}{3064187} := \frac{50}{6128374} \\ \frac{25}{3068714} := \frac{50}{6137428} \\ \frac{25}{3068741} := \frac{50}{6137482} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{3071864} := \frac{50}{6143728} \\ \frac{25}{3074186} := \frac{50}{6148372} \\ \frac{25}{3086174} := \frac{50}{6172348} \\ \frac{25}{3086417} := \frac{50}{6172834} \\ \frac{25}{3086714} := \frac{50}{6173428} \\ \frac{25}{3086741} := \frac{50}{6173482} \\ \frac{25}{3087164} := \frac{50}{6174328} \\ \frac{25}{3087416} := \frac{50}{6174832} \\ \frac{25}{3106874} := \frac{50}{6213748} \\ \frac{25}{3108674} := \frac{50}{6217348} \\ \frac{25}{3140687} := \frac{50}{6281374} \\ \frac{25}{3140867} := \frac{50}{6281734} \\ \frac{25}{3160874} := \frac{50}{6321748} \\ \frac{25}{3164087} := \frac{50}{6328174} \\ \frac{25}{3170864} := \frac{50}{6341728} \\ \frac{25}{3174086} := \frac{50}{6348172} \\ \frac{25}{3186074} := \frac{50}{6372148} \\ \frac{25}{3186407} := \frac{50}{6372814} \\ \frac{25}{3187064} := \frac{50}{6374128} \\ \frac{25}{3187406} := \frac{50}{6374812} \\ \frac{25}{3406187} := \frac{50}{6812374} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{3406871} := \frac{50}{6813742} \\ \frac{25}{3407186} := \frac{50}{6814372} \\ \frac{25}{3408617} := \frac{50}{6817234} \\ \frac{25}{3408671} := \frac{50}{6817342} \\ \frac{25}{3408716} := \frac{50}{6817432} \\ \frac{25}{3410687} := \frac{50}{6821374} \\ \frac{25}{3410867} := \frac{50}{6821734} \\ \frac{25}{3416087} := \frac{50}{6832174} \\ \frac{25}{3417086} := \frac{50}{6834172} \\ \frac{25}{3418607} := \frac{50}{6837214} \\ \frac{25}{3418706} := \frac{50}{6837412} \\ \frac{25}{3607184} := \frac{50}{7214368} \\ \frac{25}{3607418} := \frac{50}{7214836} \\ \frac{25}{3608174} := \frac{50}{7216348} \\ \frac{25}{3608417} := \frac{50}{7216834} \\ \frac{25}{3617084} := \frac{50}{7234168} \\ \frac{25}{3617408} := \frac{50}{7234816} \\ \frac{25}{3618074} := \frac{50}{7236148} \\ \frac{25}{3618407} := \frac{50}{7236814} \\ \frac{25}{3640718} := \frac{50}{7281436} \\ \frac{25}{3640817} := \frac{50}{7281634} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{3641708} := \frac{50}{7283416} \\ \frac{25}{3641807} := \frac{50}{7283614} \\ \frac{25}{3670814} := \frac{50}{7341628} \\ \frac{25}{3670841} := \frac{50}{7341682} \\ \frac{25}{3671084} := \frac{50}{7342168} \\ \frac{25}{3671408} := \frac{50}{7342816} \\ \frac{25}{3674081} := \frac{50}{7348162} \\ \frac{25}{3674108} := \frac{50}{7348216} \\ \frac{25}{3680714} := \frac{50}{7361428} \\ \frac{25}{3680741} := \frac{50}{7361482} \\ \frac{25}{3681074} := \frac{50}{7362148} \\ \frac{25}{3681407} := \frac{50}{7362814} \\ \frac{25}{3684071} := \frac{50}{7368142} \\ \frac{25}{3684107} := \frac{50}{7368214} \\ \frac{25}{3706184} := \frac{50}{7412368} \\ \frac{25}{3706418} := \frac{50}{7412836} \\ \frac{25}{3706814} := \frac{50}{7413628} \\ \frac{25}{3706841} := \frac{50}{7413682} \\ \frac{25}{3708164} := \frac{50}{7416328} \\ \frac{25}{3708416} := \frac{50}{7416832} \\ \frac{25}{3710684} := \frac{50}{7421368} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{3714068} := \frac{50}{7428136} \\ \frac{25}{3716084} := \frac{50}{7432168} \\ \frac{25}{3716408} := \frac{50}{7432816} \\ \frac{25}{3718064} := \frac{50}{7436128} \\ \frac{25}{3718406} := \frac{50}{7436812} \\ \frac{25}{3740618} := \frac{50}{7481236} \\ \frac{25}{3740681} := \frac{50}{7481362} \\ \frac{25}{3740816} := \frac{50}{7481632} \\ \frac{25}{3741068} := \frac{50}{7482136} \\ \frac{25}{3741608} := \frac{50}{7483216} \\ \frac{25}{3741806} := \frac{30}{7483612} \\ \frac{25}{3768140} := \frac{50}{4521768} \\ \frac{25}{3806174} := \frac{50}{7612348} \\ \frac{25}{3806417} := \frac{50}{7612834} \\ \frac{25}{3806714} := \frac{50}{7613428} \\ \frac{25}{3806741} := \frac{50}{7613482} \\ \frac{25}{3807164} := \frac{50}{7614328} \\ \frac{25}{3807416} := \frac{50}{7614832} \\ \frac{25}{3810674} := \frac{50}{7621348} \\ \frac{25}{3814067} := \frac{50}{7628134} \\ \frac{25}{3816074} := \frac{50}{7632148} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{3816407} := \frac{50}{7632814} \\ \frac{25}{3816740} := \frac{50}{7634128} \\ \frac{25}{3817064} := \frac{50}{7634128} \\ \frac{25}{3817406} := \frac{50}{7634812} \\ \frac{25}{3840617} := \frac{50}{7681234} \\ \frac{25}{3840671} := \frac{50}{7681342} \\ \frac{25}{3840716} := \frac{50}{7681432} \\ \frac{25}{3841067} := \frac{50}{7682134} \\ \frac{25}{3841607} := \frac{50}{7683214} \\ \frac{25}{3841706} := \frac{40}{7683412} \\ \frac{25}{3846170} := \frac{40}{6153872} \\ \frac{25}{3861470} := \frac{50}{6178352} \\ \frac{25}{4061738} := \frac{50}{8123476} \\ \frac{25}{4061837} := \frac{50}{8123674} \\ \frac{25}{4061873} := \frac{50}{8123746} \\ \frac{25}{4063187} := \frac{50}{8126374} \\ \frac{25}{4063718} := \frac{50}{8127436} \\ \frac{25}{4063817} := \frac{50}{8127634} \\ \frac{25}{4067138} := \frac{50}{8134276} \\ \frac{25}{4067381} := \frac{50}{8134762} \\ \frac{25}{4068137} := \frac{50}{8136274} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{4068371} := \frac{50}{8136742} \\ \frac{25}{4068713} := \frac{50}{8137426} \\ \frac{25}{4068731} := \frac{50}{8137462} \\ \frac{25}{4071368} := \frac{50}{8142736} \\ \frac{25}{4071638} := \frac{50}{8143276} \\ \frac{25}{4071836} := \frac{50}{8143672} \\ \frac{25}{4071863} := \frac{50}{8143726} \\ \frac{25}{4073186} := \frac{50}{8146372} \\ \frac{25}{4073618} := \frac{50}{8147236} \\ \frac{25}{4073681} := \frac{50}{8147362} \\ \frac{25}{4073816} := \frac{50}{8147632} \\ \frac{25}{4081367} := \frac{50}{8162734} \\ \frac{25}{4081637} := \frac{50}{8163274} \\ \frac{25}{4081736} := \frac{50}{8163472} \\ \frac{25}{4083617} := \frac{50}{8167234} \\ \frac{25}{4083671} := \frac{50}{8167342} \\ \frac{25}{4083716} := \frac{50}{8167432} \\ \frac{25}{4086173} := \frac{50}{8172346} \\ \frac{25}{4086317} := \frac{50}{8172634} \\ \frac{25}{4086713} := \frac{50}{8173426} \\ \frac{25}{4086731} := \frac{50}{8173462} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{4087163} := \frac{50}{8174326} \\ \frac{25}{4087316} := \frac{50}{8174632} \\ \frac{25}{4106738} := \frac{50}{8213476} \\ \frac{25}{4106837} := \frac{50}{8213674} \\ \frac{25}{4106873} := \frac{50}{8213746} \\ \frac{25}{4107368} := \frac{50}{8214736} \\ \frac{25}{4108367} := \frac{50}{8216734} \\ \frac{25}{4108673} := \frac{50}{8217346} \\ \frac{25}{4130687} := \frac{50}{8261374} \\ \frac{25}{4130867} := \frac{50}{8261734} \\ \frac{25}{4136708} := \frac{50}{8273416} \\ \frac{25}{4136807} := \frac{50}{8273614} \\ \frac{25}{4137068} := \frac{50}{8274136} \\ \frac{25}{4138067} := \frac{50}{8276134} \\ \frac{25}{4160738} := \frac{50}{8321476} \\ \frac{25}{4160837} := \frac{50}{8321674} \\ \frac{25}{4160873} := \frac{50}{8321746} \\ \frac{25}{4163087} := \frac{50}{8326174} \\ \frac{25}{4163708} := \frac{50}{8327416} \\ \frac{25}{4163807} := \frac{50}{8327614} \\ \frac{25}{4170638} := \frac{50}{8341276} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{4170836} := \frac{50}{8341672} \\ \frac{25}{4170863} := \frac{50}{8341726} \\ \frac{25}{4173086} := \frac{50}{8346172} \\ \frac{25}{4173608} := \frac{50}{8347216} \\ \frac{25}{4173806} := \frac{50}{8347612} \\ \frac{25}{4180637} := \frac{50}{8361274} \\ \frac{25}{4180736} := \frac{50}{8361472} \\ \frac{25}{4183607} := \frac{50}{8367214} \\ \frac{25}{4183706} := \frac{50}{8367412} \\ \frac{25}{4186073} := \frac{50}{8372146} \\ \frac{25}{4186307} := \frac{50}{8372614} \\ \frac{25}{4187063} := \frac{50}{8374126} \\ \frac{25}{4187306} := \frac{50}{8374612} \\ \frac{25}{4306187} := \frac{50}{8612374} \\ \frac{25}{4306871} := \frac{50}{8613742} \\ \frac{25}{4307186} := \frac{50}{8614372} \\ \frac{25}{4308617} := \frac{50}{8617234} \\ \frac{25}{4308671} := \frac{50}{8617342} \\ \frac{25}{4308716} := \frac{50}{8617432} \\ \frac{25}{4310687} := \frac{50}{8621374} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{4310867} := \frac{50}{8621734} \\ \frac{25}{4316087} := \frac{50}{8632174} \\ \frac{25}{4317086} := \frac{50}{8634172} \\ \frac{25}{4318607} := \frac{50}{8637214} \\ \frac{25}{4318706} := \frac{50}{8637412} \\ \frac{25}{4360718} := \frac{50}{8721436} \\ \frac{25}{4360817} := \frac{50}{8721634} \\ \frac{25}{4361708} := \frac{50}{8723416} \\ \frac{25}{4361807} := \frac{50}{8723614} \\ \frac{25}{4367081} := \frac{50}{8734162} \\ \frac{25}{4367108} := \frac{50}{8734216} \\ \frac{25}{4368071} := \frac{50}{8736142} \\ \frac{25}{4368107} := \frac{50}{8736214} \\ \frac{25}{4370618} := \frac{50}{8741236} \\ \frac{25}{4370681} := \frac{50}{8741362} \\ \frac{25}{4370816} := \frac{50}{8741632} \\ \frac{25}{4371068} := \frac{50}{8742136} \\ \frac{25}{4371608} := \frac{50}{8743216} \\ \frac{25}{4371806} := \frac{50}{8743612} \\ \frac{25}{4380617} := \frac{50}{8761234} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{25}{4380671} := \frac{50}{8761342} \\ \frac{25}{4380716} := \frac{50}{8761432} \\ \frac{25}{4381067} := \frac{50}{8762134} \\ \frac{25}{4381607} := \frac{50}{8763214} \\ \frac{25}{4381706} := \frac{50}{8763412} \\ \frac{25}{4736810} := \frac{50}{5684172} \\ \frac{25}{6318470} := \frac{50}{7582164} \\ \frac{25}{6348710} := \frac{50}{7618452} \\ \frac{25}{6871430} := \frac{50}{8245716} \\ \frac{25}{7143680} := \frac{50}{8572416} \\ \frac{25}{10348976} := \frac{50}{31046928} \\ \frac{25}{10349876} := \frac{50}{31049628} \\ \frac{25}{10489736} := \frac{50}{31469208} \\ \frac{25}{10498736} := \frac{50}{31496208} \\ \frac{25}{10673489} := \frac{50}{21346978} \\ \frac{25}{10673849} := \frac{50}{21347698} \\ \frac{25}{10673948} := \frac{50}{21347896} \\ \frac{25}{10673984} := \frac{50}{21347968} \\ \frac{25}{10674398} := \frac{50}{21348796} \end{array}$$

11 Narcissistic Type Representations

11.1 Narcissistic Type Representations for 25

$$25 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^0}{2^4 + 5^2}$$

11.2 Pattern-Type with 25

$$1\ 25 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 + 5^3}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2\ 25 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{12} + 5^4}{2^2 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$3\ 25 := \frac{3^3 + 2^{11} + 5^5}{3^1 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$4\ 25 := \frac{4^1 + 2^{12} + 5^5}{4^1 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$5\ 25 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{10} + 5^2}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$6\ 25 := \frac{6^7 + 2^6 + 5^6}{6^3 + 2^8 + 5^0}$$

$$7\ 25 := \frac{-7^4 + 2^0 + 5^5}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8\ 25 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{16} + 5^8}{8^3 + 2^4 + 5^2}$$

$$9\ 25 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{10} + 5^6}{9^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

11.3 Narcissistic Type Representations for 2025

$$2025 := \frac{2^{15} + 0^0 + 2^{20} + 5^1}{2^4 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^1}$$

12 Semi-Selfie Representations

12.1 Semi-Selfie Representations for 25

$$25^3 := 15625 = (1 + 5 - 6 + 25)^3$$

$$25^4 := 390625 = (3 + 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\ = (3 - 9 + 06 + 25)^4$$

$$25^5 := 9765625 = (-97 + 65 + 62 - 5)^5$$

$$25^6 := 244140625 = (2 + 4 - 4 + 14 + 06 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ = (24 - 4 - 14 - 06 + 25)^6 \\ = (-2 + 44 + 14 - 06 - 25)^6$$

$$25^7 := 6103515625 = (61 + 03 - 5 - 15 + 6 - 25)^7 \\ = (61 + 035 + 1 - 5 - 62 - 5)^7 \\ = (610 - 3 - 515 - 62 - 5)^7$$

12.2 Semi-Selfie Representations for 2025

In this case, instead of considering 2025 we have considered 20+25.

$$(20 + 25)^2 := 2025 = (20 + 25)^2$$

$$(20 + 25)^3 := 91125 = (9 + 11 + 25)^3$$

$$(20 + 25)^4 := 4100625 = (4 + 10 + 06 + 25)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned} (20 + 25)^5 &:= 184528125 = (18 - 45 - 2 + 81 - 2 - 5)^5 \\ &= (-18 - 45 + 2 + 81 + 25)^5 \\ &= (1 - 8 - 45 - 28 + 125)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (20 + 25)^6 &:= 8303765625 = (83 + 037 + 6 - 56 - 25)^6 \\ &= (83 + 03 - 7 - 65 + 6 + 25)^6 \\ &= (8 - 30 + 37 - 6 + 5 + 6 + 25)^6 \end{aligned}$$

13 Amicable-Type Pattern with 25

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 5 \times 1 + 2 \times 10 & \Leftrightarrow & \quad 52 := 2 \times 1 + 5 \times 10 \\ 250 &:= 5 \times 10 + 20 \times 10 & \Leftrightarrow & \quad 520 := 2 \times 10 + 50 \times 10 \\ 25250 &:= 5 \times 10 + 2520 \times 10 & \Leftrightarrow & \quad 52520 := 2 \times 10 + 5250 \times 10 \\ 2525250 &:= 5 \times 10 + 252520 \times 10 & \Leftrightarrow & \quad 5252520 := 2 \times 10 + 525250 \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

14 Power Representations

14.1 Power of 2

$$2025 := 2^{10} + 2^9 + 2^8 + 2^7 + 2^6 + 2^5 + 2^4 - 2^3 + 2^0.$$

14.2 Power 2

$$25 := 5^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &:= 45^2 \\ &:= (20 + 25)^2 \\ &:= (3^2 + 6^2)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10000 + 2025 &:= 12^2 + 109^2 \\ &:= 19^2 + 108^2 \\ &:= 24^2 + 107^2 \\ &:= 45^2 + 100^2 \\ &:= 53^2 + 96^2 \\ &:= 75^2 + 80^2 \end{aligned}$$

14.3 Power 5

$$\begin{aligned}11 \times 10000 + 2025 &= 112025 := 1^5 + 2^5 + 3^5 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 9^5 \\21 \times 10000 + 2025 &= 212025 := 1^5 + 2^5 + 3^5 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 10^5 \\23 \times 10000 + 2025 &= 232025 := 4^5 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 11^5 \\33 \times 10000 + 2025 &= 332025 := 4^5 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 10^5 + 11^5 \\64 \times 10000 + 2025 &= 642025 := 1^5 + 2^5 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 11^5 + 13^5 \\74 \times 10000 + 2025 &= 742025 := 1^5 + 2^5 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 10^5 + 11^5 + 13^5\end{aligned}$$

15 Square-Power Patterns for 25 and 2025

15.1 Square-Power Patterns for 25

1.

$$\begin{aligned}25^2 &:= 625 \\225^2 &:= 50625 \\2225^2 &:= 4950625 \\22225^2 &:= 493950625\end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned}45^2 &:= 2025 \\455^2 &:= 207025 \\4555^2 &:= 20748025 \\45555^2 &:= 2075258025\end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}25^2 &:= 625 \\255^2 &:= 65025 \\2555^2 &:= 6528025 \\25555^2 &:= 653058025\end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned}45^2 &:= 2025 \\495^2 &:= 245025 \\4995^2 &:= 24950025 \\49995^2 &:= 2499500025\end{aligned}$$

15.2 Square-Power Patterns for 2025

1.

$$\begin{aligned} 2025^2 &:= 4100625 \\ 20025^2 &:= 401000625 \\ 200025^2 &:= 40010000625 \\ 2000025^2 &:= 4000100000625 \end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned} 2025^2 &:= 4100625 \\ 20125^2 &:= 405015625 \\ 201125^2 &:= 40451265625 \\ 2011125^2 &:= 4044623765625 \end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned} 2025^2 &:= 4100625 \\ 20225^2 &:= 409050625 \\ 202225^2 &:= 40894950625 \\ 2022225^2 &:= 4089393950625 \end{aligned}$$

16 Power-Plus-Minus Equalities

16.1 Power-Plus-Minus Equalities for 25

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= 2^3 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 4^2 - 10^0 = 23 + 30 + 30 + 42 - 100 \\ &:= 1^1 + 2^3 + 4^0 + 5^2 - 10^1 = 11 + 23 + 40 + 52 - 101 \\ &:= 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 3^2 + 10^2 = 12 - 26 - 31 - 32 + 102 \\ &:= 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 3^6 + 10^3 = 15 - 22 - 35 - 36 + 103 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 10^4 + 10^4 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 104 + 104 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 10^5 + 10^5 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 105 + 105 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 10^6 + 10^6 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 106 + 106 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 10^7 + 10^7 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 107 + 107 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 10^8 + 10^8 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 108 + 108 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 10^9 + 10^9 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 109 + 109 \\ &:= 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 4^2 - 11^0 = 23 + 30 + 40 + 42 - 110 \\ &:= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 4^1 - 11^1 = 22 + 33 + 40 + 41 - 111 \\ &:= 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 11^2 = 11 - 25 - 30 - 43 + 112 \\ &:= 1^8 - 2^8 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 11^3 = 18 - 28 - 33 - 45 + 113 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 11^4 + 11^4 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 114 + 114 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 11^5 + 11^5 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 115 + 115 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 11^6 + 11^6 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 116 + 116 \\ &:= 1^3 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 11^7 + 11^7 = 13 - 40 + 52 - 117 + 117 \end{aligned}$$

16.2 Power-Plus-Minus Equalities for 2025

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2025} &:= 7^3 + 41^2 + 154^0 &= 73 + 412 + 1540 \\ &:= -1^7 + 45^2 + 159^0 &= -17 + 452 + 1590 \\ &:= 10^3 + 32^2 + 160^0 &= 103 + 322 + 1600 \\ &:= 1^2 + 44^2 + 70^0 + 87^1 &= 12 + 442 + 700 + 871 \\ &:= 2^2 + 44^2 + 72^0 + 84^1 &= 22 + 442 + 720 + 841 \\ &:= 3^2 + 44^2 + 76^0 + 79^1 &= 32 + 442 + 760 + 791 \\ &:= 4^2 + 44^2 + 72^1 + 82^0 &= 42 + 442 + 721 + 820 \\ &:= 10^2 + 43^2 + 74^0 + 75^1 &= 102 + 432 + 740 + 751 \\ &:= 14^2 + 42^2 + 64^1 + 82^0 &= 142 + 422 + 641 + 820 \\ &:= 16^2 + 41^2 + 58^0 + 87^1 &= 162 + 412 + 580 + 871 \\ &:= 19^2 + 40^2 + 63^1 + 80^0 &= 192 + 402 + 631 + 800 \\ &:= 21^2 + 39^2 + 62^1 + 80^0 &= 212 + 392 + 621 + 800 \\ &:= 24^2 + 37^2 + 62^0 + 79^1 &= 242 + 372 + 620 + 791 \\ &:= 26^2 + 36^2 + 52^1 + 88^0 &= 262 + 362 + 521 + 880 \\ &:= 27^2 + 35^2 + 70^0 + 70^1 &= 272 + 352 + 700 + 701 \\ &:= 28^2 + 34^2 + 56^0 + 84^1 &= 282 + 342 + 560 + 841 \end{aligned}$$

17 Factorial-Power Equalities

17.1 Factorial-Power Equalities for 25

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{25} &= -1! + 2! + 3! \times 4! - 5! &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^4 - 4^3 - 5^2 \\ &= -1! + 2! - 5! + 3! \times 4! &= 1^1 + 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^4 - 4^3 \\ &= 1! - (3! - 2!) \times 4! + 5! &= 1^1 + 3^4 + 2^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 \\ &= -1! + 3! \times 4! + 2! - 5! &= 1^1 + 3^4 - 4^3 + 2^5 - 5^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= 1! + 3! \times 5! - 6! + 4! &&= 1^6 \times 3^4 - 5^1 \times 6^3 + 4^5 \\ &= -1! + 4! \times 3! + 2! - 5! &&= 1^1 - 4^3 + 3^4 + 2^5 - 5^2 \\ &= 1! + 4! + 3! \times 5! - 6! &&= 1^6 \times 4^5 + 3^4 - 5^1 \times 6^3 \\ &= 1! + 5! - (3! - 2!) \times 4! &&= 1^1 - 5^2 + 3^4 + 2^5 - 4^3 \\ &= -1! - 5! + 3! \times 4! + 2! &&= 1^1 - 5^2 + 3^4 - 4^3 + 2^5 \\ &= 1! + 5! + 4! \times (2! - 3!) &&= 1^1 - 5^2 - 4^3 + 2^5 + 3^4 \\ &= -1! - 5! + 4! \times 3! + 2! &&= 1^1 - 5^2 - 4^3 + 3^4 + 2^5 \\ &= 1! + 6! - 5! \times 3! + 4! &&= -1^6 \times 6^3 \times 5^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 \\ &= 2! - 1! + 3! \times 4! - 5! &&= 2^2 - 1^5 + 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^1 \\ &= 2! - 1! - 5! + 3! \times 4! &&= 2^2 - 1^5 + 5^1 + 3^4 - 4^3 \\ &= (2! - 3!) \times 4! + 1! + 5! &&= 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^3 - 1^5 + 5^1 \\ &= 2! + 4! \times 3! - 1! - 5! &&= 2^2 - 4^3 + 3^4 - 1^5 + 5^1 \\ &= 2! - 5! - 1! + 3! \times 4! &&= 2^2 + 5^1 - 1^5 + 3^4 - 4^3 \\ &= 2! - 5! + 3! \times 4! - 1! &&= 2^2 + 5^1 + 3^4 - 4^3 - 1^5 \\ &= (-3! + 2!) \times 4! + 1! + 5! &&= (-3^3 + 2^4 + 4^2) \times 1^5 \times 5^1 \\ &= 3! \times 4! - 1! + 2! - 5! &&= -3^3 - 4^1 - 1^4 + 2^5 + 5^2 \\ &= 3! \times 5! + 1! - 6! + 4! &&= 3^4 - 5^1 \times 1^6 \times 6^3 + 4^5 \\ &= 4! + 1! + 3! \times 5! - 6! &&= 4^5 \times 1^6 + 3^4 - 5^1 \times 6^3 \\ &= 4! + 1! + 6! - 5! \times 3! &&= 4^5 \times 1^6 - 6^3 \times 5^1 + 3^4 \\ &= 4! \times (2! - 3!) + 1! + 5! &&= 4^4 + 2^3 - 3^5 - 1^2 + 5^1 \end{aligned}$$

17.2 Factorial-Power Equalities for 2025

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 \ 2 &= (3! - 2!) \times (7! + 4! - 0!) = 3^3 + (2^7 - 7^2) \times 4^4 + 0^0 \\ &= (3! - 2!) \times (7! + 4! - 1!) = 3^3 + (2^7 - 7^2) \times 4^4 + 1^1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 \ 5 &= -1! + (3! - 2!) \times (7! + 4!) = (1^3 \times 3^4 - 2^1) \times 7^2 + 4^7 \\ &= (3! - 2!) \times (7! + 4!) - 1! = (3^4 - 2^1) \times 7^2 + 4^7 \times 1^3 \\ &= (-2! + 3!) \times (7! + 4!) - 1! = (-2^1 + 3^4) \times 7^2 + 4^7 \times 1^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 \ 2 &= (1! \times 3! - 2!) \times (7! + 4!) = 1^3 + (3^4 - 2^1) \times 7^2 + 4^7 \\ &= (1! \times 4! + 7!) \times (3! - 2!) = 1^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \times (3^4 - 2^1) \\ &= (-2! + 3! + 5! + 6!) \times 4! = 2^3 \times (-3^5 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 4^6) \\ &= (-2! + 6! + 5! + 3!) \times 4! = 2^3 \times (-6^4 - 5^2 - 3^5 + 4^6) \\ &= (3! - 2!) \times (7! \times 1! + 4!) = (3^4 - 2^1) \times 7^2 + 1^3 + 4^7 \\ &= (3! - 2!) \times (7! + 4!) \times 1! = (3^4 - 2^1) \times 7^2 + 4^7 + 1^3 \\ &= (3! - 2!) \times 7! + 5! - 4! = (-3^3 - 2^5 \times 7^4 + 5^7) \times 4^2 \end{aligned}$$

18 Fibonacci-Triangular Equalities

18.1 Fibonacci-Triangular Equalities for 2025

$$\begin{aligned} 2025 &= ((-F(1) + F(8)) \times F(9) - F(5)) \times F(4) = (T(1) \times T(8) + T(9)) \times (T(5) + T(4)) \\ &= F(4) \times (-F(5) + (-F(1) + F(8)) \times F(9)) = (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(1) \times (T(8) + T(9)) \\ &= F(4) \times (-F(5) + (-F(2) + F(8)) \times F(9)) = (T(4) + T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(8) + T(9) \\ &= F(4) \times (-F(5) + (F(8) - F(1)) \times F(9)) = (T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(8) \times T(1) + T(9)) \\ &= F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(9) \times (-F(1) + F(8))) = (T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(9) \times T(1) + T(8)) \\ &= F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(9) \times (F(8) - F(1))) = (T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(8)) \times T(1) \\ &= (-F(5) + (-F(2) + F(8)) \times F(9)) \times F(4) = (T(5) \times T(2)) + T(8) \times (T(9) + T(4)) \\ &= ((F(8) - F(1)) \times F(9) - F(5)) \times F(4) = (T(8) \times T(1) + T(9)) \times (T(5) + T(4)) \\ &= ((F(9) \times (-F(1) + F(8))) - F(5)) \times F(4) = (((T(9) \times T(1)) + T(8)) \times (T(5) + T(4))) \\ &= (F(9) \times (F(8) - F(1)) - F(5)) \times F(4) = (T(9) + T(8)) \times T(1) \times (T(5) + T(4)) \\ &= (F(9) \times (F(8) - F(2)) - F(5)) \times F(4) = T(9) + (T(8) \times (T(2) \times T(5) + T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

18.2 Factorial-Fibonacci-Triangular Equalities for 25

$$\begin{aligned}
 25 &:= (((-1! + 2!) + (3! \times 4!)) - 5!) = (((F(1) \times F(2)) \times F(3)) + F(4)) \times F(5) = (((T(1) - T(2)) + T(3)) \times T(4)) - T(5) \\
 &:= ((1! - ((3! - 2!) \times 4!)) + 5!) = (((F(1) + F(3)) - F(2)) + F(4)) \times F(5) = (((T(1) + T(3)) - T(2)) \times T(4)) - T(5) \\
 &:= (((-1! + (3! \times 4!)) + 2!) - 5!) = (((F(1) + F(3)) + F(4)) - F(2)) \times F(5) = (((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4)) - (T(2) \times T(5))) \\
 &:= (((-1! + (3! \times 4!)) - 5!) + 2!) = (((F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(5))) + F(2)) = (((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(2))) \\
 &:= (((1! + (3! \times 5!)) + 4!) - 6!) = (((F(1) \times F(3)) + (F(5) \times F(4))) + F(6)) = (T(1) + (T(3) \times ((T(5) + T(4)) - T(6)))) \\
 &:= (((1! + (3! \times 5!)) - 6!) + 4!) = (((F(1) - F(3)) \times F(5)) \times (-F(6) + F(4))) = (T(1) + (T(3) \times ((T(5) - T(6)) + T(4)))) \\
 &:= (((1! + 4!) + (5! \times 3!)) - 6!) = (((F(1) + F(4)) + F(5)) + (F(3) \times F(6))) = ((T(1) + (T(4) \times T(5))) - (T(3) \times T(6))) \\
 &:= (((1! + 4!) + 6!) - 5! \times 3!) = (((F(1) + F(4)) \times F(6)) - F(5)) - F(3) = ((-T(1) - T(4)) + ((T(6) - T(5)) \times T(3))) \\
 &:= (((1! + (5! \times 3!)) + 4!) - 6!) = (F(1) + F(5) \times F(3)) \times F(4) - F(6) = T(1) - T(5) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(6) \\
 &:= (((-1! + 2!) + (3! \times 4!)) - 5!) = (((F(1) \times F(2)) \times F(3)) + F(4)) \times F(5) = (((T(1) - T(2)) + T(3)) \times T(4)) - T(5) \\
 &:= ((1! - ((3! - 2!) \times 4!)) + 5!) = (((F(1) + F(3)) - F(2)) + F(4)) \times F(5) = (((T(1) + T(3)) - T(2)) \times T(4)) - T(5) \\
 &:= (((-1! + (3! \times 4!)) + 2!) - 5!) = (((F(1) + F(3)) + F(4)) - F(2)) \times F(5) = (((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4)) - (T(2) \times T(5))) \\
 &:= (((-1! + (3! \times 4!)) - 5!) + 2!) = (((F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(5))) + F(2)) = (((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(2))) \\
 &:= (((1! + (3! \times 5!)) + 4!) - 6!) = (((F(1) \times F(3)) + (F(5) \times F(4))) + F(6)) = (T(1) + (T(3) \times ((T(5) + T(4)) - T(6)))) \\
 &:= (((1! + (3! \times 5!)) - 6!) + 4!) = (((F(1) - F(3)) \times F(5)) \times (-F(6) + F(4))) = (T(1) + (T(3) \times ((T(5) - T(6)) + T(4)))) \\
 &:= (((1! + 4!) + (5! \times 3!)) - 6!) = (((F(1) + F(4)) + F(5)) + (F(3) \times F(6))) = ((T(1) + (T(4) \times T(5))) - (T(3) \times T(6))) \\
 &:= (((1! + 4!) + 6!) - 5! \times 3!) = (((F(1) + F(4)) \times F(6)) - F(5)) - F(3) = ((-T(1) - T(4)) + ((T(6) - T(5)) \times T(3))) \\
 &:= (((1! + (5! \times 3!)) + 4!) - 6!) = (((F(1) + (F(5) \times F(3))) \times F(4)) - F(6)) = (((T(1) - T(5)) + (T(3) \times T(4))) - T(6)) \\
 &:= (((1! + 6!) - (3! \times 5!)) + 4!) = ((F(1) + F(6)) + (F(3) \times (F(5) + F(4)))) = ((T(1) - (T(6) \times T(3))) + (T(5) \times T(4))) \\
 &:= (((1! + 6!) + 4!) - (3! \times 5!)) = (((-F(1) + F(6)) + F(4)) \times F(3)) + F(5) = (((T(1) - T(6)) + (T(4) \times T(3))) - T(5)) \\
 &:= (((1! + 6!) + 4!) - 5! \times 3!) = ((F(1) + F(6)) + ((F(4) + F(5)) \times F(3))) = (T(1) - (((T(6) - T(4)) - T(5)) \times T(3))) \\
 &:= (((1! + 6!) - 5! \times 3!) + 4!) = (((F(1) + F(6)) + F(5)) \times F(3)) - F(4) = (((T(1) - T(6)) - T(5)) + (T(3) \times T(4))) \\
 &:= (((2! - 1!) + (3! \times 4!)) - 5!) = (((F(2) \times F(1)) \times F(3)) + F(4)) \times F(5) = (((-T(2) + T(1)) + T(3)) \times T(4)) - T(5) \\
 &:= (((2! - 5!) - 1!) + (3! \times 4!)) = (((F(2) + F(5)) - F(1)) \times (F(3) + F(4))) = ((-T(2) \times T(5)) + ((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4))) \\
 &:= (((2! - 5!) + (4! \times 3!)) - 1!) = (((F(2) \times F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(3))) \times F(1)) = ((-T(2) \times T(5)) + (T(4) \times (T(3) + T(1)))) \\
 &:= (((3! \times 5! + 4!) - 6!) + 1!) = (((F(3) \times (F(5) + F(4))) + F(6)) + F(1)) = ((T(3) \times ((T(5) + T(4)) - T(6))) + T(1)) \\
 &:= (((3! \times 5!) - (6! - 1!)) + 4!) = ((-F(3) - F(5)) + (F(6) \times (F(1) + F(4)))) = (((T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(6))) - T(1)) - T(4)) \\
 &:= (((-3! \times 5!) + (6! + 4!)) + 1!) = ((-F(3) - F(5)) + (F(6) \times (F(4) + F(1)))) = ((T(3) \times ((T(5) - T(6)) + T(4))) + T(1)) \\
 &:= (((4! + 1!) + (3! \times 5!)) - 6!) = ((F(4) \times (F(1) + (F(3) \times F(5)))) - F(6)) = ((-T(4) - T(1)) + (T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(6)))) \\
 &:= (((4! + 1!) + 6!) - 5! \times 3!) = (((F(4) + F(1)) \times F(6)) - F(5)) - F(3) = (-T(4) - T(1)) + ((T(6) - T(5)) \times T(3)) \\
 &:= (((4! \times (2! - 3!)) + 1!) + 5!) = (((F(4) + F(2)) + F(3)) - F(1)) \times F(5) = ((T(4) \times ((-T(2) + T(3)) + T(1))) - T(5)) \\
 &:= (((4! \times 3! - 1!) + 2!) - 5!) = (((F(4) + F(3)) + F(1)) - F(2)) \times F(5) = ((T(4) \times (T(3) + T(1))) - (T(2) \times T(5))) \\
 &:= (((4! \times 3! - 1!) - 5!) + 2!) = (((F(4) + F(3)) \times F(1)) \times F(5)) \times F(2) = ((T(4) \times (T(3) + T(1))) - (T(5) \times T(2))) \\
 &:= (((4! \times 3!) + 2!) - 1!) - 5!) = (((F(4) + F(3)) + F(2)) - F(1)) \times F(5) = ((T(4) \times ((T(3) - T(2)) + T(1))) - T(5)) \\
 &:= (((4! + (3! \times 5!)) + 1!) - 6!) = ((F(4) \times ((F(3) \times F(5)) + F(1))) - F(6)) = (((T(4) \times T(3)) - T(5)) + T(1)) - T(6) \\
 &:= (((4! + (3! \times 5!)) - 6!) + 1!) = (-F(4) + (F(3) \times ((F(5) + F(6)) + F(1)))) = (((T(4) \times T(3)) - T(5)) - T(6)) + T(1) \\
 &:= (((4! + (5! \times 3!)) - 6!) + 1!) = (((F(4) + F(5)) \times F(3)) + F(6)) + F(1) = (((T(4) \times T(5)) - (T(3) \times T(6))) + T(1)) \\
 &:= (((4! + 6!) - 5! \times 3!) + 1!) = (((F(4) - F(6)) \times F(5)) \times (-F(3) + F(1))) = (((T(4) - T(6)) + T(5)) \times T(3)) + T(1) \\
 &:= ((5! + (4! \times (2! - 3!))) + 1!) = (((F(5) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(3))) + F(1)) = (-T(5) + (T(4) \times ((-T(2) + T(3)) + T(1)))) \\
 &:= (((-5! + (4! \times 3!)) - 1!) + 2!) = (((F(5) + F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(1))) + F(2)) = (-T(5) + (T(4) \times ((T(3) + T(1)) - T(2)))) \\
 &:= (((-5! + (4! \times 3!)) + 2!) - 1!) = (((F(5) + F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(2))) + F(1)) = (-T(5) + (T(4) \times ((T(3) - T(2)) + T(1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Prime Pattern with Digits 0, 2, 5 and 1**

11 2025 111 5202 11
 10211 2025 111 5202 11201
 100110211 2025 111 5202 112011001
 15511100110211 2025 111 5202 11201100111551
 15215511100110211 2025 111 5202 11201100111551251
 1215215511100110211 2025 111 5202 1120110011155125121
 120511215215511100110211 2025 111 5202 112011001115512512115021
 1525120511215215511100110211 2025 111 5202 1120110011155125121150215251
 11211525120511215215511100110211 2025 111 5202 11201100111551251211502152511211
 122211211525120511215215511100110211 2025 111 5202 112011001115512512115021525112112221
 15155122211211525120511215215511100110211 2025 111 5202 11201100111551251211502152511211222155151
 15115155122211211525120511215215511100110211 2025 111 5202 11201100111551251211502152511211222155151151

• **Prime Pattern with Digits 0, 2, 5, 9 and 1**

1 2025 9 5202 1
 10111 2025 9 5202 11101
 150110111 2025 9 5202 111011051
 1151150110111 2025 9 5202 1110110511511
 1511151150110111 2025 9 5202 111011051151151151
 10111511151150110111 2025 9 5202 1110110511511511511101
 152110111511151150110111 2025 9 5202 11101105115115115111011251
 1221152110111511151150110111 2025 9 5202 111011051151151151110112511221
 1051221152110111511151150110111 2025 9 5202 111011051151151151110112511221501
 1221051221152110111511151150110111 2025 9 5202 111011051151151151110112511221501221
 12251221051221152110111511151150110111 2025 9 5202 1110110511511511511101125112215012215221
 150512251221051221152110111511151150110111 2025 9 5202 11101105115115115111011251122150122152215051
 12522150512251221051221152110111511151150110111 2025 9 5202 1110110511511511511101125112215012215221505122521

19.2 Embedded Non-Palindromic Prime Patterns with 2025

These patterns are unlimited. These may go how long you want.

• **Embedded Symmetric Prime Pattern with Digits 0, 2, 5 and 1**

11 2025 11
15511 2025 11551
1215511 2025 1155121
151215511 2025 115512151
1002151215511 2025 1155121512001
1121002151215511 2025 1155121512001211
15511121002151215511 2025 11551215120012111551
15215511121002151215511 2025 11551215120012111551251
101215215511121002151215511 2025 115512151200121115512512101
1502101215215511121002151215511 2025 1155121512001211155125121012051
11521502101215215511121002151215511 2025 11551215120012111551251210120512511
111521502101215215511121002151215511 2025 115512151200121115512512101205125111
101111521502101215215511121002151215511 2025 115512151200121115512512101205125111101
1015101111521502101215215511121002151215511 2025 1155121512001211155125121012051251111015101
1221015101111521502101215215511121002151215511 2025 1155121512001211155125121012051251111015101221
... ..

• **Embedded Symmetric Prime Pattern with Digits 0, 2, 5 and 3**

32 2025 23
352232 2025 232253
3352232 2025 2322533
323352232 2025 232253323
30022323352232 2025 23225332322003
3502230022323352232 2025 2322533232200322053
30233502230022323352232 2025 23225332322003220533203
353230233502230022323352232 2025 232253323220032205332032353
302353230233502230022323352232 2025 232253323220032205332032353203
3303302353230233502230022323352232 2025 2322533232200322053320323532033033
353523303302353230233502230022323352232 2025 232253323220032205332032353203303325353
3052353523303302353230233502230022323352232 2025 2322533232200322053320323532033033253532503
30323052353523303302353230233502230022323352232 2025 23225332322003220533203235320330332535325032303
330323052353523303302353230233502230022323352232 2025 232253323220032205332032353203303325353250323033
... ..

● **Embedded Symmetric Prime Pattern with Digits 0, 2, 5 and 7**

7 2025 7
77 2025 77
7777 2025 7777
7027777 2025 7777207
7027027777 2025 7777207207
72727027027777 2025 77772072072727
772272727027027777 2025 777720720727272277
7525772272727027027777 2025 7777207207272722775257
77527525772272727027027777 2025 77772072072727227752572577
755777527525772272727027027777 2025 777720720727272277525725777557
752755777527525772272727027027777 2025 777720720727272277525725777557257
7072752755777527525772272727027027777 2025 7777207207272722775257257775572572707
752227072752755777527525772272727027027777 2025 777720720727272277525725777557257270722257
72525752227072752755777527525772272727027027777 2025 77772072072727227752572577755725727072225752527
... ..

● **Embedded Symmetric Prime Pattern with Digits 0, 2, 5 and 9**

955 2025 559
955955 2025 559559
905955955 2025 559559509
9292905955955 2025 5595595092929
959292905955955 2025 559559509292959
9552959292905955955 2025 5595595092929592559
920029552959292905955955 2025 559559509292959255920029
929920029552959292905955955 2025 559559509292959255920029929
9522929920029552959292905955955 2025 5595595092929592559200299292259
95529522929920029552959292905955955 2025 55955950929295925592002992922592559
955595529522929920029552959292905955955 2025 559559509292959255920029929225925595559
9955955595529522929920029552959292905955955 2025 5595595092929592559200299292259255955595599
95999955955595529522929920029552959292905955955 2025 55955950929295925592002992922592559555955999959
... ..

20 Fixed Digits Repetitions Primes Patterns for 2025

20.1 Length 6

221471	819499
22147 2025 1	81949 2025 9
22147 2025 2025 1	81949 2025 2025 9
22147 2025 2025 2025 1	81949 2025 2025 2025 9
22147 2025 2025 2025 2025 1	81949 2025 2025 2025 2025 9
22147 2025 2025 2025 2025 2025 1	81949 2025 2025 2025 2025 2025 9

20.2 Length 7

486977
486 2025 977
486 2025 2025 977
486 2025 2025 2025 977
486 2025 2025 2025 2025 977
486 2025 2025 2025 2025 2025 977
486 2025 2025 2025 2025 2025 2025 977

In all the three examples, the next line in each pattern is no more prime number. These are fixed length prime patterns.

21 Palindromic-Type Patterns and Expressions

21.1 Palindromic-Type Patterns for 25

1.

$$\begin{aligned}847 &:= 11 \times 52 + 25 \times 11 &= 572 + 275 \\8547 &:= 111 \times 52 + 25 \times 111 &= 5772 + 2775 \\85547 &:= 1111 \times 52 + 25 \times 1111 &= 57772 + 27775 \\855547 &:= 11111 \times 52 + 25 \times 11111 &= 577772 + 277775\end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}7777 &:= 101 \times 52 + 25 \times 101 &= 5252 + 2525 \\77077 &:= 1001 \times 52 + 25 \times 1001 &= 52052 + 25025 \\770077 &:= 10001 \times 52 + 25 \times 10001 &= 520052 + 250025 \\7700077 &:= 100001 \times 52 + 25 \times 100001 &= 5200052 + 2500025\end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned}847 &:= 11 \times 52 + 25 \times 11 &= 572 + 275 \\7777 &:= 11 \times 502 + 205 \times 11 &= 5522 + 2255 \\77077 &:= 11 \times 5002 + 2005 \times 11 &= 55022 + 22055 \\770077 &:= 11 \times 50002 + 20005 \times 11 &= 550022 + 220055\end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned}7777 &:= 101 \times 52 + 25 \times 101 &= 5252 + 2525 \\71407 &:= 101 \times 502 + 205 \times 101 &= 50702 + 20705 \\707707 &:= 101 \times 5002 + 2005 \times 101 &= 505202 + 202505 \\7070707 &:= 101 \times 50002 + 20005 \times 101 &= 5050202 + 2020505\end{aligned}$$

21.2 Palindromic-Type Patterns for 2025

1.

$$\begin{aligned}79497 &:= 11 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 11 &= 57222 + 22275 \\802197 &:= 111 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 111 &= 577422 + 224775 \\8029197 &:= 1111 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 1111 &= 5779422 + 2249775 \\80299197 &:= 11111 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 11111 &= 57799422 + 22499775\end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}729927 &:= 101 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 101 &= 525402 + 204525 \\7234227 &:= 1001 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 100 &= 5207202 + 2027025 \\72277227 &:= 10001 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 10001 &= 52025202 + 20252025 \\722707227 &:= 100001 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 100001 &= 520205202 + 202502025\end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned}79497 &:= 11 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 11 &= 57222 + 22275 \\792297 &:= 11 \times 52002 + 2025 \times 11 &= 572022 + 220275 \\7920297 &:= 11 \times 520002 + 2025 \times 11 &= 5720022 + 2200275 \\79200297 &:= 11 \times 5200002 + 2025 \times 11 &= 57200022 + 22000275\end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned}729927 &:= 101 \times 5202 + 2025 \times 101 &= 525402 + 204525 \\7274727 &:= 101 \times 52002 + 2025 \times 101 &= 5252202 + 2022525 \\72722727 &:= 101 \times 520002 + 2025 \times 101 &= 52520202 + 20202525 \\727202727 &:= 101 \times 5200002 + 2025 \times 101 &= 525200202 + 202002525\end{aligned}$$

21.3 Palindromic-Type Expressions for 25

1.

$$\begin{aligned}5995 &:= 0 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 0 = 0275 + 5720 \\7106 &:= 1 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 1 = 1375 + 5731 \\8217 &:= 2 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 2 = 2475 + 5742 \\9328 &:= 3 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 3 = 3575 + 5753 \\10439 &:= 4 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 4 = 4675 + 5764 \\11550 &:= 5 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 5 = 5775 + 5775 \\12661 &:= 6 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 6 = 6875 + 5786 \\13772 &:= 7 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 7 = 7975 + 5797 \\14883 &:= 8 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 8 = 9075 + 5808 \\15994 &:= 9 \ 25 \times 11 + 11 \times 52 \ 9 = 10175 + 5819\end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}55045 &:= 0 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 0 = 02525 + 52520 \\65246 &:= 1 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 1 = 12625 + 52621 \\75447 &:= 2 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 2 = 22725 + 52722 \\85648 &:= 3 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 3 = 32825 + 52823 \\95849 &:= 4 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 4 = 42925 + 52924 \\106050 &:= 5 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 5 = 53025 + 53025 \\116251 &:= 6 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 6 = 63125 + 53126 \\126452 &:= 7 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 7 = 73225 + 53227 \\136653 &:= 8 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 8 = 83325 + 53328 \\146854 &:= 9 \mathbf{25} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{52} 9 = 93425 + 53429\end{aligned}$$

We observe that not all the expressions symmetric as expected.

21.4 Palindromic-Type Expressions for 2025

1.

$$\begin{aligned}594495 &:= 0 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 0 = 022275 + 572220 \\704506 &:= 1 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 1 = 132275 + 572231 \\814517 &:= 2 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 2 = 572242 + 242275 \\924528 &:= 3 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 3 = 572253 + 352275 \\1034539 &:= 4 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 4 = 572264 + 462275 \\1144550 &:= 5 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 5 = 572275 + 572275 \\1254561 &:= 6 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 6 = 572286 + 682275 \\1364572 &:= 7 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 7 = 572297 + 792275 \\1474583 &:= 8 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 8 = 572308 + 902275 \\1584594 &:= 9 \mathbf{2025} \times 11 + 11 \times \mathbf{5202} 9 = 572319 + 1012275\end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}
 5458545 &:= 0 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 0 = 0204525 + 5254020 \\
 6468646 &:= 1 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 1 = 1214525 + 5254121 \\
 7478747 &:= 2 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 2 = 2224525 + 5254222 \\
 8488848 &:= 3 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 3 = 3234525 + 5254323 \\
 9498949 &:= 4 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 4 = 4244525 + 5254424 \\
 10509050 &:= 5 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 5 = 5254525 + 5254525 \\
 11519151 &:= 6 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 6 = 6264525 + 5254626 \\
 12529252 &:= 7 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 7 = 7274525 + 5254727 \\
 13539353 &:= 8 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 8 = 8284525 + 5254828 \\
 14549454 &:= 9 \mathbf{2025} \times 101 + 101 \times \mathbf{5202} 9 = 9294525 + 5254929
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that not all the expressions are symmetric as expected.

22 1 to 200 Numbers in Terms of 2025-5202

$0 := 2 \times 0 \times 255202$	$16 := (2 \times 0 - 2) \times (5 + 5 - 20 + 2)$
$1 := (202 + 5) / (5 + 202)$	$17 := (20 - 25) / 5 + 20 - 2$
$2 := 2 + 0 \times 255202$	$18 := 20 + 2552 \times 0 - 2$
$3 := 20 \times 2 - 55 + 20 - 2$	$19 := (20 + 25) / 5 + 20 / 2$
$4 := 2 + 0 \times 25520 + 2$	$20 := 20 + 2552 \times 0 \times 2$
$5 := (20 + 25) / (5 + 2 + 02)$	$21 := 20 / 2 + 5 / 5 + 20 / 2$
$6 := (20 + 2) \times 5 - (52 + 0) \times 2$	$22 := 20 - 2552 \times 0 + 2$
$7 := 20 + 25 / 5 - 20 + 2$	$23 := 20 - 2 \times 5 - 5 + 20 - 2$
$8 := 20 - 25 - 5 + 20 - 2$	$24 := 20 - 2 + 5 + 5 - 2 - 02$
$9 := 2 \times 0 \times 25 + 5 + 2 + 02$	$25 := 202 + 5 \times 5 - 202$
$10 := 202 + 5 + 5 - 202$	$26 := 20 - 2 - 5 - 5 + 20 - 2$
$11 := 20 - 25 / 5 - 2 - 02$	$27 := 2 + 025 + 52 \times 0 \times 2$
$12 := 2 + 0 \times 255 + 20 / 2$	$28 := 20 + 25 + 5 - 20 - 2$
$13 := 20 \times (2 \times 5 + 5) / 20 - 2$	$29 := 2 + 02 + 5 + 5 \times 2 \times 02$
$14 := 2 + 025 + 5 - 20 + 2$	$30 := (20 + 25 - 5 + 20) / 2$
$15 := 20 + 25 + (5 - 20) \times 2$	$31 := (20 + 25) / 5 + 20 + 2$

$$32 := 20 + 25 + 5 - 20 + 2$$

$$33 := 20 - 25/5 + 20 - 2$$

$$34 := 2 \times 0 + 25 + 5 + 2 + 02$$

$$35 := 2 \times 0 + 2 + 55 - 20 - 2$$

$$36 := 20 + 25 - 5 - 2 \times 02$$

$$37 := 20 + 2 + 55 - 20 \times 2$$

$$38 := 2 \times (025 + 5) - 20 - 2$$

$$39 := 2 - 0 \times 2 + 55 - 20 + 2$$

$$40 := 20 + 2 - 5 + 5 + 20 - 2$$

$$41 := 2 + 02 + 55 - 20 + 2$$

$$42 := 2 \times 0 + 25 - 5 + 20 + 2$$

$$43 := 20 + 25 + 52 \times 0 - 2$$

$$44 := 20 + 2 - 5 + 5 + 20 + 2$$

$$45 := 20 - 25 + 52 - 02$$

$$46 := 20 - 2 + 5 + 5 + 20 - 2$$

$$47 := 20 - 25 + 52 + 0 \times 2$$

$$48 := 20 + 25 + 5 - 2 + 0 \times 2$$

$$49 := 20 - 25 + 52 + 02$$

$$50 := (-20 - 2 - 5 + 52) \times 02$$

$$51 := 2 \times 0 \times 2 + 55 - 2 \times 02$$

$$52 := 20 + 25 + 5 - 2 \times 0 + 2$$

$$53 := 2 \times 0 + 255 - 202$$

$$54 := 20 + 25 + 5 + 2 + 02$$

$$55 := 202 + 55 - 202$$

$$56 := 2 \times 0 + (2 \times 55 + 2)/02$$

$$57 := 20 + 25 + 5 \times 2 + 02$$

$$58 := 20 + 25 - 5 + 20 - 2$$

$$59 := 2 \times 0 \times 2 + 55 + 2 \times 02$$

$$60 := (20 + 25 + 5 - 20) \times 2$$

$$61 := -2 \times 02 + 55 + 20/2$$

$$62 := 20 + 25 - 5 + 20 + 2$$

$$63 := 20/2 + 55 - 2 + 0 \times 2$$

$$64 := 2 \times 0 + 2 \times 5 + 52 + 02$$

$$65 := (20 - 25) \times (5 - 20 + 2)$$

$$66 := 2 \times 0 + 2 \times (55 - 20 - 2)$$

$$67 := 20 + 2 - 5 + 52 - 02$$

$$68 := 2 \times (02^5 + 5 - 20) \times 2$$

$$69 := 20 - 2 + 55 - 2 - 02$$

$$70 := 20 + 25/5 \times 20/2$$

$$71 := 20 + 2 - 5 + 52 + 02$$

$$72 := 202 - 5 \times 52/02$$

$$73 := 20 + 255 - 202$$

$$74 := (2 + 0 \times 2 + 55 - 20) \times 2$$

$$75 := 20 + 25 - (5 - 20) \times 2$$

$$76 := 20 + 2 + 55 - 2/02$$

$$77 := 20 \times 2 + 55 - 20 + 2$$

$$78 := 20 \times 25/5 - 20 - 2$$

$$79 := 20 + 2 + 55 + 2 \times 0 + 2$$

$$80 := 20 + 2 \times 5 + 52 - 02$$

$$81 := 20 + 2 + 55 + 2 + 02$$

$$82 := 2 \times (025 + 5) + 20 + 2$$

$$83 := 20 - 2 + 55 + 20/2$$

$$84 := (-2 - 02 + 5 \times 5) \times 2 \times 02$$

$$85 := 20 \times 2 - 5 + (5 + 20) \times 2$$

$$86 := 20 - (2 - 55 + 20) \times 2$$

$$87 := (2 - 025) \times 5 + 202$$

$$88 := 20 - 2 + (55 - 20) \times 2$$

$$89 := 20 \times 2 - 5 + 52 + 02$$

$$90 := 20 + 25 + 5 + 20 \times 2$$

$$91 := (202 + 5 - 5 - 20)/2$$

$$92 := 2 + 02 \times (55 - 20/2)$$

$$93 := 202 - 5 - 52 \times 02$$

$$94 := 2 + 02 \times 55 - 20 + 2$$

$$95 := 20 + 25 + 52 - 02$$

$$96 := 20 \times 2 + 55 + 2/02$$

$$97 := 20 - 25 \times 5 + 202$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98 &:= 2 \times 0 \times 25 + 5 \times 20 - 2 \\ 99 &:= 20 + 25 + 52 + 02 \\ 100 &:= 2 \times 025 + 52 - 02 \\ 101 &:= 2 \times 0 + 2 - 5 + 52 \times 02 \\ 102 &:= (202 - 5 + 5 + 2) / 02 \\ 103 &:= 202 + 5 - 52 \times 02 \\ 104 &:= 2 \times 025 + 52 + 02 \\ 105 &:= 20 \times 25 + 5 - 20^2 \\ 106 &:= 2 \times (0255 - 202) \\ 107 &:= 202 - 55 - 20 \times 2 \\ 108 &:= 20 + 2 \times 55 - 20 - 2 \\ 109 &:= 20/2 - 5 + 52 \times 02 \\ 110 &:= (20 + 2 \times 5 + 5 + 20) \times 2 \\ 111 &:= (20 + 2) \times 5 + 5 - 2 - 02 \\ 112 &:= 20 - 2 \times 55 + 202 \\ 113 &:= 20 \times (2 + 5) - 5 - 20 - 2 \\ 114 &:= (-20 + 25 + 52) \times 02 \\ 115 &:= 20 \times 2 + 5 \times (5 + 20/2) \\ 116 &:= 20 - 2 \times (5 - 52) + 02 \\ 117 &:= 2 + 025 \times 5 - 20/2 \\ 118 &:= 20 \times 2/5 + 5 \times (20 + 2) \\ 119 &:= 20/2 + 5 + 52 \times 02 \\ 120 &:= (20 + 25 - 5 + 20) \times 2 \\ 121 &:= 20 + 2 - 5 + 52 \times 02 \\ 122 &:= 20 \times 25/5 + 20 + 2 \\ 123 &:= 20 + 25 \times 5 - 20 - 2 \\ 124 &:= 20 + 2 \times (55 - 2) - 02 \\ 125 &:= 202 - 55 - 20 - 2 \\ 126 &:= 2 + 025 \times 5 - 2/02 \\ 127 &:= 2 + 025 \times 5 + 2 \times 0 \times 2 \\ 128 &:= 20 + 2 \times (55 - 2) + 02 \\ 129 &:= 202 - 55 - 20 + 2 \\ 130 &:= 20^2/5 + 52 - 02 \\ 131 &:= 20 + 2 + 5 + 52 \times 02 \\ 132 &:= 202 - (55 - 20) \times 2 \\ 133 &:= 20 - 2 + 5 \times (5 + 20 - 2) \\ 134 &:= 20^2/5 + 52 + 02 \\ 135 &:= 20 + 25 + 5 \times (20 - 2) \\ 136 &:= 2 \times (02 + 55) + 20 + 2 \\ 137 &:= 202 - 55 - 20/2 \\ 138 &:= (20 + 2 - 5 + 52) \times 02 \\ 139 &:= (20 - 2) \times 5 + (5 + 2)^{02} \\ 140 &:= 2 \times 0 + 2 \times (55 - 20) \times 2 \\ 141 &:= 20 + 25 \times 5 - 2 - 02 \\ 142 &:= 2 \times 0 + (2 + 5 + 5)^2 - 02 \\ 143 &:= 202 - 5 - 52 - 02 \\ 144 &:= (20 - 25 - 5 - 2)^{02} \\ 145 &:= (20 + 2) \times 5 - 5 + 20 \times 2 \\ 146 &:= (20 - 2 + 55) \times 2 + 0 \times 2 \\ 147 &:= 202 - 55 + 2 - 02 \\ 148 &:= 20 + 2 \times 55 + 20 - 2 \\ 149 &:= 20 + 25 + 52 \times 02 \\ 150 &:= 2 \times 0 + 2 \times 55 + 20 \times 2 \\ 151 &:= 2 + 02 - 55 + 202 \\ 152 &:= 2 \times (025 + 52) - 02 \\ 153 &:= 202 + 5 - 52 - 02 \\ 154 &:= (20 + 2 + 55 + 2 \times 0) \times 2 \\ 155 &:= 202 + 5 - 52 + 0 \times 2 \\ 156 &:= 2 \times (025 + 52) + 02 \\ 157 &:= 20/2 - 55 + 202 \\ 158 &:= (20 + 2 + 55 + 2) \times 02 \\ 159 &:= 202 - 5 \times 5 - 20 + 2 \\ 160 &:= (202 - ((5/5 + 20) \times 2)) \\ 161 &:= 202 - 5/5 - 20 \times 2 \\ 162 &:= 202 + 5 - 5 - 20 \times 2 \\ 163 &:= 20 \times 2 + 5 \times (5 + 20) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$164 := 202 + (5/5 - 20) \times 2$$

$$165 := 20 - 2 - 55 + 202$$

$$166 := 20 + 2 \times (55 + 20 - 2)$$

$$167 := 20 + 25 \times 5 + 20 + 2$$

$$168 := 20 - 2 + (55 + 20) \times 2$$

$$169 := 20 + 2 - 55 + 202$$

$$170 := 20 + 2 \times 55 + 20 \times 2$$

$$171 := 202 - 5 - 52/02$$

$$172 := 20 + 2 \times (55 + 20) + 2$$

$$173 := 20 \times 2 \times 5 - 5 - 20 - 2$$

$$174 := 202 - 5 - 5 - 20 + 2$$

$$175 := (20 - 25) \times (5 - 20 \times 2)$$

$$176 := (20 - 2^5 + 5 \times 20) \times 2$$

$$177 := (20 - 25) \times 5 + 202$$

$$178 := -2 \times (02 + 5 + 5) + 202$$

$$179 := 202 - 5/5 - 20 - 2$$

$$180 := 202 - 5 + 5 - 20 - 2$$

$$181 := 202 + 5/5 - 20 - 2$$

$$182 := 202 - (5 + 5) \times 2 + 0 \times 2$$

$$183 := 202 - 5/5 - 20 + 2$$

$$184 := 202 + 5 - 5 - 20 + 2$$

$$185 := 202 + 5/5 - 20 + 2$$

$$186 := 202 + (-5 - 5 + 2) \times 02$$

$$187 := 202 - 55 + 20 \times 2$$

$$188 := 20^2 - 5 - 5 - 202$$

$$189 := 2 - 02 \times 5 + 5 + 202$$

$$190 := (20 - 25 + 5 \times 20) \times 2$$

$$191 := 2/02 - (5 - 5 \times 20) \times 2$$

$$192 := 20 - 25 - 5 + 202$$

$$193 := 2/02 - 5 - 5 + 202$$

$$194 := 202 - 5 - 5 + 2 + 0 \times 2$$

$$195 := 20 - 2 - 5 \times 5 + 202$$

$$196 := 2 + 02 - 5 - 5 + 202$$

$$197 := 202 + 5 - 5 \times 2 + 0 \times 2$$

$$198 := 20^2 + 5 - 5 - 202$$

$$199 := 202 - 5 \times 5 + 20 + 2$$

$$200 := 2 \times 0 \times 25 + 5 \times 20 \times 2$$

23 Upside Down and Mirror Looking

23.1 Upside Down and Mirror Looking for 25

(i)

$$\begin{array}{c} | + | | + | + | | + | \\ 8 + | + 8 + 8 \\ | + 6 + 8 + 9 + | \end{array}$$

It contains three expressions. The first and second are **universal**, i.e., **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. The first is only with numbers 0 and 1. The second one is with 1 and 8. The third expression is with 1, 6, 8 and 9. It is only **upside-down**.

(ii)

$$\begin{array}{c} 25 \\ | + 5 + 8 + 8 + 2 + | \\ | + 2 + 6 + | + 9 + 5 + | \end{array}$$

Here also we have three expressions. The first is directly 25. The second one is with 1, 2, 5 and 8. Both the expressions are **universal**, i.e., **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. The third expression is with the numbers 1, 2, 5, 6 and 9. Due to 6 and 9 it is only **upside-down**.

23.2 Upside Down and Mirror Looking for 2025

(i)

$$\begin{array}{c} 96 + 9 | 6 + | + 9 | 6 + 96 \\ | + 69 + 6 | 9 + | + 6 | 9 + 6 | 9 + 96 + | \\ 6 + 6 + 69 + 6 | 9 + 6 | 9 + 6 | 9 + 69 + 9 + 9 \end{array}$$

The above three expressions are with 1, 6 and 9. These expressions representing 2025 are **upside-down**

(ii)

$$\begin{array}{c}
 | | + | 0 0 | + | + | 0 0 | + | | \\
 | + 8 + 8 | + 8 | 8 + 8 8 + 8 + 8 8 + 8 | 8 + 8 8 + | 8 + 8 + |
 \end{array}$$

The first expression is with 0 and 1 and the second expression is with 1 and 8. Both the expressions are **universal**, i.e., **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

(iii)

$$\begin{array}{c}
 | + | + | + 2 + 2 + 2 + | | + | | + 2 2 2 + 2 2 2 + 5 5 5 + 5 5 5 + | | + | | + 5 + 5 + 5 + + | + | + | \\
 | + 2 + 2 + 2 + | 0 0 | + | 0 0 | + 5 + 5 + 5 + |
 \end{array}$$

(iv)

$$\begin{array}{c}
 | + 2 + 2 + 2 2 + 2 2 + 2 5 + 2 2 2 + | 0 0 | + 5 5 5 + 5 2 + 5 5 + 5 5 + 5 + 5 + | \\
 | + | | + | 2 + 5 | | + 5 | 2 + 5 2 + 8 + | | + | + 8 + 2 5 + 2 1 5 + 1 5 + 2 1 1 + | | + | |
 \end{array}$$

Above there are four expressions for 2025 given in (iii) and (iv). The first three are with 0, 1, 2 and 5. The forth expression is with 1, 2, 5 and 8. All the four expressions are **universal**, i.e., **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

24 Three Color Representations for Each Month of 2025

24.1 Months 1 and 2

24.2 Months 3 and 4

24.3 Months 5 and 6

24.4 Months 7 and 8

24.5 Months 9 and 10

24.6 Months 11 and 12

25 Universal Magic Squares with 25 and 2025

The number 25 is with only two digits, i.e., 2 and 5. The number 2025 is formed by three digits 0, 2 and 5. The numbers 2 and 5 are upside-down and mirror looking. In case of mirror looking 2 become 5 and by as 2. The number 0 is always upside-down and mirror looking. It remains always the same. Based on this observation, we shall write below magic squares with digits 2 and 5, and with digits 0, 2 and 5 resulting in universal magic squares.

25.1 Universal Semi-Magic Square of Order 3

Below are two **semi-magic** squares of order 3 having the digits 0, 2 and 5.

20	55	02
05	22	50
52	00	25

525	000	252
202	555	020
050	222	505

The first **semi-magic** square is having 2-digits in each cell while the second **semi-magic** square is with 3-digits in each cell. The **semi-magic** sums are 77 and 777 respectively.

25.2 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 4

25.2.1 Universal Pandiagonal with 25

Below is a **pandiagonal** squares of order 4 having two digits 2 and 5:

2552	5255	2222	5525
2225	5522	2555	5252
5555	2252	5225	2522
5222	2525	5552	2255

The above **pandiagonal universal** magic square of order 4 is with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4}(2, 5) := 15554$.

25.2.2 Universal with 2025

Below is a squares of order 4 having three digits 0, 2 and 5:

2550	5052	2020	5225
2025	5220	2552	5050
5252	2050	5025	2520
5020	2525	5250	2052

It is universal magic square of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4}(0, 2, 5) := 14847$. In this case the upside-down and mirror looking sums are different, i.e., $Su_{4 \times 4}(0, 2, 5) = Sm_{4 \times 4}(2, 5) := 8484$.

25.3 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 5

Below is a **pandiagonal** squares of order 5 with three digits 0, 2 and 5:

2552	5222	2200	0055	5525
2255	0025	5552	2522	5200
5522	2500	5255	2225	0052
5225	2252	0022	5500	2555
0000	5555	2525	5252	2222

The above **pandiagonal universal** magic square of order 5 is with magic sum $S_{5 \times 5}(0, 2, 5) := 15554$.

25.3.1 Universal with 2025

We observe that the above magic square is with digits 0, 2 and 5 but it doesn't have the year 2025. Below is another magic square of order 5 with same digits 0, 2 and 5 but it is with 2025:

0202	0505	2020	2525	5050
2520	5025	0250	0502	2005
0550	2002	2505	5020	0225
5005	0220	0525	2050	2502
2025	2550	5002	0205	0520

The above **pandiagonal universal** magic square of order 5 is with magic sum $S_{5 \times 5}(0, 2, 5) = Sm_{5 \times 5}(0, 2, 5) := 10302$. In case of mirror-looking it with the same sum, but in case of upside down the magic sum is different, i.e., $Su_{5 \times 5}(0, 2, 5) := 13029$. In all the three situations the magic square is always **pandiagonal**.

25.4 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 7

Below is a **pandiagonal** squares of order 7 with three digits 0, 2 and 5:

2525	2020	5252	5050	0202	0505	0000
0502	0005	2500	2025	5220	5052	0250
5020	0252	0550	0002	2505	2000	5225
2005	5200	5025	0220	0552	0050	2502
0052	2550	2002	5205	5000	0225	0520
0200	0525	0020	2552	2050	5202	5005
5250	5002	0205	0500	0025	2520	2052

The above **pandiagonal universal** magic square of order 7 is with magic sum $S_{7 \times 7}(0, 2, 5) := 15554$. This magic square is with one of the entries as 2025.

Remark 25.1. *As in case of order 7, we don't have the number 2025 as an entry in the magic square of order 5. The reason is that if we choose the possibility of having the 2025 as one of the entry, then in this case, we have a universal magic square of order 5 but with different sum in case of mirror looking situation. See below an example:*

The above magic square is with 3 digits 0, 2 and 5. Still we can have a **pandiagonal universal** magic square of order 7 only with two digits 2 and 5:

222222	225225	252252	255255	522522	525525	552552
525522	552525	222552	225222	252225	255252	522255
255225	522252	525255	552522	222525	225552	252222
225525	252552	255222	522225	525252	552255	222522
552252	222255	225522	252525	255552	522222	525225
522552	525222	552225	222252	225255	252522	255525
252255	255522	522525	525552	552222	222225	225252

The above **pandiagonal universal** magic square of order 7 is with magic sum $S_{7 \times 7}(2, 5) := 2555553$.

25.5 Universal Magic Squares of Order 8

Below we shall give two magic squares with digits 0, 2 and 5 and another as **pandiagonal** with two digits 2 and 5.

2505	5022	5552	2255	5220	0550	0202	2025
5225	0502	0250	2020	2555	5052	5522	2205
2222	5505	5055	2552	2050	0220	0525	5202
2002	0225	0520	5250	2252	5555	5005	2522
5550	2220	2525	5002	0222	2005	5255	0552
0252	2055	5205	0522	5502	2225	2520	5050
5020	2550	2202	5525	0505	5222	2052	0255
0555	5252	2022	0205	5025	2502	2250	5520

The above magic square of order 8 with digits 0, 2 and 5 having one of entry as the number 2025. The magic sums is $S_{8 \times 8}(0, 2, 5) := 23331$,

Below is another magic square only with two digits 2 and 5:

222222	555522	255255	522555	225222	552522	252255	525555
255555	522255	222522	555222	252555	525255	225522	552222
522522	255222	555555	222255	525522	252222	552555	225255
555255	222555	522222	255522	552255	225555	525222	252522
222225	555525	255252	522552	225225	552525	252252	525552
255552	522252	222525	555225	252552	525252	225525	552225
522525	255225	555552	222252	525525	252225	552552	225252
555252	222552	522225	255525	552252	225552	525225	252525

The above magic square is **pandiagonal**, where the blocks of order 4 are also **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. The magic sums are: $S_{8 \times 8}(2, 5) := 3111108$ and $S_{4 \times 4}(2, 5) := 1555554$.

25.6 Universal Pandiagonal and Bimagic Squares of Order 9

Below are two types of magic squares with three digits 0, 2 and 5.

- **Bimagic with 3-Digits 0, 2 and 5**

2222	2500	2055	5205	5552	5020	0250	0525	0002
5250	5525	5002	0222	0500	0055	2205	2552	2020
0205	0552	0020	2250	2525	2002	5222	5500	5055
2000	2255	2522	5052	5220	5505	0025	0202	0550
5025	5202	5550	0000	0255	0522	2052	2220	2505
0052	0220	0505	2025	2202	2550	5000	5255	5522
2555	2022	2200	5520	5005	5252	0502	0050	0225
5502	5050	5225	0555	0022	0200	2520	2005	2252
0520	0005	0252	2502	2050	2225	5555	5022	5200

It is **universal bimagic** square of order 9 with digits 0, 2 and 5. It contains one of the entry as a number 2025. The magic and **bimagic** sums are $S_{9 \times 9}(0, 2, 5) := 23331$ and $Sb_{9 \times 9}(0, 2, 5) := 98865567$

● **Pandiagonal with 3-Digits 0, 2 and 5**

2250	0502	5025	5252	2505	0020	0255	5500	2022
0022	5255	2500	2025	0250	5502	5020	2252	0505
5505	2020	0252	0500	5022	2255	2502	0025	5250
2000	0222	5555	5002	2225	0550	0005	5220	2552
0552	5005	2220	2555	0000	5222	5550	2002	0225
5225	2550	0002	0220	5552	2005	2222	0555	5000
2520	0052	5205	5522	2055	0200	0525	5050	2202
0202	5525	2050	2205	0520	5052	5200	2522	0055
5055	2200	0522	0050	5202	2525	2052	0205	5520

It is **universal pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 with digits 0, 2 and 5. It contains one of the entry as a number 2025. The magic sum is $S_{9 \times 9}(0, 2, 5) := 23331$.

● **Bimagic with 2-Digits 2 and 5**

52525252	52252222	52222525	25522225	25252552	25225222	22522522	22255225	22222252
25522522	25255225	25222252	22525252	22252222	22222525	52522225	52252552	52225222
22522225	22252552	22225222	52522522	52255225	52222252	25525252	25252222	25222525
52222222	52522525	52255252	25222552	25525222	25252225	22225225	22522252	22252522
25225225	25522252	25252522	22222222	22522525	22255252	52222552	52525222	52252225
22222552	22525222	22252225	52225225	52522252	52252522	25222222	25522525	25255252
52252525	52225252	52522222	25255222	25222225	25522552	22252252	22222522	22525225
25252252	25222522	25525225	22252525	22225252	22522222	52255222	52222225	52522552
22255222	22222225	22522552	52252252	52222522	52525225	25252525	25222525	25522222

It is **universal bimagic** square of order 9 with digits 2 and 5. The magic and **bimagic** sums are $S_{9 \times 9}(0, 2, 5) := 299999997$ and $Sb_{9 \times 9}(0, 2, 5) := 11638163616381600$

● **Pandiagonal with 2-Digits 2 and 5**

52522225	25222552	22255222	22522252	52222522	25255225	25522222	22222525	52255252
25255252	22522222	52222525	52255222	25522225	22222552	22255225	52522252	25222522
22222522	52255225	25522252	25222525	22255252	52522222	52222552	25255222	22522225
52252525	25525252	22222222	22252552	52525222	25222225	25252522	22525225	52222252
25222252	22252522	52525225	52222222	25252525	22525252	22222225	52252552	25525222
22525222	52222225	25252552	25525225	22222252	52252522	52525252	25222222	22252525
52225225	25252252	22522522	22225252	52252222	25522525	25225222	22252225	52522552
25522552	22225222	52252225	52522522	25225225	22252252	22522525	52225252	25252222
22252222	52522525	25225252	25252225	22522552	52225222	52252252	25522522	22225225

It is **universal pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 with digits 2 and 5. The magic sum is $S_{9 \times 9}(0, 2, 5) := 299999997$.

25.7 Universal Magic Squares of Order 10

● **Universal Magic Square with 4-Digits 0, 2, 5 and 8**

0000	8820	5222	0205	5552	5002	2025	2255	0550	2588
2205	0202	2088	0052	2520	5200	5550	0525	5055	8822
8855	5525	0505	2500	5288	2250	5022	0220	0002	2052
5522	5250	0055	2020	0500	0288	2202	2552	8825	5005
2050	5000	0225	5255	2222	8852	0020	5588	2505	0502
0252	0555	8802	5088	0050	2525	5205	2022	5520	2200
5020	2252	2550	0522	0255	5505	8888	5202	2000	0025
2502	0088	5500	2225	8805	2055	0552	5050	0222	5220
0588	2005	2220	5502	5025	0022	2555	8800	5252	0250
5225	2522	5052	8850	2002	0520	0200	0005	2288	5555

It is universal magic square of order 10 with 4-digits 0, 2, 5 and 8. It contains one of the entries as 2025. The magic sum is $S_{10 \times 10}(0, 2, 5) := 32219$.

• **Universal Magic Square with 3-Digits 0, 2 and 5**

555555	055250	025222	550520	022025	052550	250220	222022	520052	220055
222520	550550	250055	555025	220250	025555	022052	520220	052022	055222
055022	022220	520520	220555	025055	222052	052222	550250	555550	250025
022222	025052	555022	250250	520555	550055	222550	220025	055220	052520
250052	052555	550220	025022	222222	055025	555250	022055	220520	520550
550025	520022	055550	052055	555052	220220	025520	250222	022250	222555
052250	222025	220052	520222	550022	022520	055055	025550	250555	555220
220550	555055	022555	222220	055520	250022	520025	052052	550222	025250
520055	250520	222250	022550	052220	555222	220022	055555	025025	550052
025220	220222	052025	055052	250550	520250	550555	555520	222055	022022

It is universal magic square of order 10 with 3-digits 0, 2 and 5. Since cell entries are with 6-digits, the number 2025 appears in two cells combined with another numbers, i.e., **022025** and **220250**.

26 Magic Squares with Magic Sum 25

26.1 Magic Squares of Order 5

Below are three magic squares of order 5 with magic sum 25. These are constructed with **sequential entries** from -7 to 17, i.e., $\{-7, -6, \dots, 16, 17\}$.

	pan	25	25	25	25	25			25					
25	-7	-1	5	11	17	25		14	17	-3	-1	-2	25	
25	10	16	-3	-2	4	25		-6	4	9	2	16	25	
25	2	3	9	15	-4	25		-5	3	5	7	15	25	
25	14	-5	1	7	8	25		10	8	1	6	0	25	
	6	12	13	-6	0	25		12	-7	13	11	-4	25	
5x5	25	25	25	25	25	25		5x5	25	25	25	25	25	25

					25	
	8	3	4	15	-5	25
	1	5	9	17	-7	25
	6	7	2	-1	11	25
	-3	-2	14	0	16	25
	13	12	-4	-6	10	25
5x5	25	25	25	25	25	25

First one is **pandiagonal** magic square. The second one is **bordered** magic square, and the third one is **cornered** magic square.

26.2 Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are 6 magic squares of order 10 with magic sum 25. These are constructed with **sequential entries** from -47 to 52, i.e., $\{-47, -46, \dots, 51, 52\}$.

10x10	mgc		25	10x10	mgc		25
		43 38 -32 36 -30 -34 -44 50 -46 44	25			43 38 -32 36 -30 -34 -44 50 -46 44	25
		-35 -22 -28 32 34 21 -17 23 -23	40 25			-35 -1 10 -29 30 -9 18 -21 22	40 25
		41 -25 16 14 -13 20 -12 -10	30 -36 25			41 -26 27 2 7 -18 19 -6 15	-36 25
		-37 -24 -14 1 6 -5 8 19 29	42 25			-37 34 -25 6 -5 26 -17 14 -13	42 25
		48 -19 -8 -4 7 2 5 13 24	-43 25			48 3 -2 31 -22 11 -10 23 -14	-43 25
		-47 31 -6 10 -3 4 -1 11 -26	52 25			-47 0 9 -28 29 -8 17 -20 21	52 25
		45 26 12 3 0 9 -2 -7 -21	-40 25			45 -27 28 1 8 -19 20 -7 16	-40 25
		-41 25 15 -9 18 -15 17 -11	-20 46 25			-41 33 -24 5 -4 25 -16 13 -12	46 25
		47 28 33 -27 -29 -16 22 -18	27 -42 25			47 4 -3 32 -23 12 -11 24 -15	-42 25
		-39 -33 37 -31 35 39 49 -45	51 -38 25			-39 -33 37 -31 35 39 49 -45	51 -38 25
		25 25 25 25 25 25 25 25	25			25 25 25 25 25 25 25 25	25

First magic square is bordered magic square. The second one is **block-bordered** magic square. The internal block is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8. It is composed of 4 equal sums magic squares of order 4.

10x10	mgc										25	10x10	mgc										25
	-44	49	46	-41	0	5	-27	32	-23	28	25		-45	-47	51	49	48	-42	46	-40	-39	44	25
	50	-45	-40	45	11	-6	31	-26	27	-22	25		50	52	-46	-44	-43	47	-41	45	-37	42	25
	-47	52	47	-42	-5	10	30	-25	26	-21	25		-23	28	-5	10	-10	15	-13	18	43	-38	25
	51	-46	-43	48	3	2	-24	29	-20	25	25		27	-22	12	-7	13	-8	20	-15	41	-36	25
	-35	39	38	-32	9	-4	-15	19	18	-12	25		-21	26	-6	11	16	-11	-14	19	40	-35	25
	40	-34	-33	37	-7	12	20	-14	-13	17	25		25	-20	9	-4	-9	14	17	-12	-34	39	25
	-31	36	-39	44	6	-1	-16	21	14	-9	25		24	-19	5	-3	4	3	-1	7	38	-33	25
	35	-30	43	-38	7	-2	22	-17	-8	13	25		22	-17	0	8	1	2	6	-2	-32	37	25
	34	-29	42	-37	4	1	-19	24	15	-10	25		-16	21	-31	35	-29	33	-24	-26	30	32	25
	-28	33	-36	41	-3	8	23	-18	-11	16	25		-18	23	36	-30	34	-28	29	31	-25	-27	25
	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25		25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

These two magic squares are **striped** magic squares. The second one is **double digits bordered** magic square. The internal block is striped magic square of order 6.

10x10	mgc										25	10x10	mgc										25
	-11	15	14	-8	-15	20	27	-22	38	-33	25		-35	40	45	-40	20	-15	21	-25	-10	24	25
	16	-10	-9	13	19	-14	-23	28	-32	37	25		-30	35	47	-42	-8	13	-16	30	15	-19	25
	-16	22	-19	23	18	-13	26	-21	-37	42	25		37	-32	-43	48	-18	23	6	-1	-26	31	25
	21	-17	24	-18	-12	17	-20	25	41	-36	25		39	-34	-41	46	-4	9	0	5	10	-5	25
	-31	-26	-29	33	30	32	35	-24	40	-35	25		36	-31	42	-37	32	-27	1	4	11	-6	25
	36	31	34	-28	-25	-27	-30	29	-34	39	25		-28	33	-38	43	-14	19	-2	7	26	-21	25
	-45	49	-47	51	48	-42	46	-40	-39	44	25		34	-29	44	-39	25	-20	8	-3	12	-7	25
	50	-44	52	-46	-43	47	-41	45	43	-38	25		-33	38	-36	41	-13	18	2	3	-12	17	25
	-5	11	0	3	-3	7	6	4	-7	9	25		-47	51	50	-44	29	14	-11	-22	-23	28	25
	10	-6	5	2	8	-2	-1	1	12	-4	25		52	-46	-45	49	-24	-9	16	27	22	-17	25
	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25		25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

These two magic squares are **striped** magic squares. The first one is **cornered-type** magic square.

26.3 Magic Squares of Order 25

Below are three magic squares of order 25 with magic sum 25. These are constructed with **sequential entries**: $\{-311, -310, \dots, 312, 313\}$

pan	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	
25	-311	-92	-28	186	250	105	294	-237	-173	16	-129	-40	149	218	-193	287	-274	-85	4	73	53	117	206	-230	-141	25
25	172	261	-300	-111	-17	-162	27	91	305	-256	224	-207	-118	-54	160	-10	79	273	-263	-74	-219	-155	59	128	192	25
25	-100	-36	183	247	-289	291	-245	-181	38	102	-43	146	235	-201	-132	-277	-63	1	65	279	134	203	-233	-144	45	25
25	258	-303	-89	-25	164	19	113	302	-259	-170	-190	-126	-57	157	221	76	265	-271	-77	12	-158	56	120	209	-222	25
25	-14	175	239	-292	-103	-248	-184	30	94	313	143	232	-204	-115	-51	-71	-2	87	276	-285	195	-216	-147	42	131	25
25	271	-265	-76	-7	82	62	126	190	-221	-152	-297	-108	-19	170	259	89	308	-253	-164	25	-120	-56	163	227	-209	25
25	-1	68	282	-279	-65	-235	-146	48	137	201	181	245	-291	-97	-33	-178	36	100	289	-242	238	-198	-134	-45	144	25
25	-268	-79	10	74	268	123	212	-224	-160	54	-91	-22	167	256	-305	300	-261	-167	22	111	-59	155	219	-187	-123	25
25	85	274	-282	-68	-4	-149	40	129	198	-213	242	-294	-105	-16	178	33	97	311	-250	-186	-206	-112	-48	141	230	25
25	-82	7	71	285	-276	204	-227	-138	51	115	-30	184	253	-308	-94	-239	-175	14	108	297	152	216	-195	-131	-37	25
25	103	292	-244	-180	34	-136	-42	147	236	-200	280	-281	-62	2	66	46	135	199	-232	-143	-288	-99	-35	179	248	25
25	-169	20	109	303	-258	222	-189	-125	-61	158	13	77	266	-270	-81	-226	-157	57	121	210	165	254	-302	-88	-24	25
25	309	-247	-183	31	95	-50	139	233	-203	-114	-284	-70	-6	88	277	132	196	-215	-151	43	-102	-13	176	240	-296	25
25	17	106	295	-241	-172	-192	-128	-39	150	214	69	288	-273	-84	5	-140	49	118	207	-229	251	-310	-96	-27	187	25
25	-255	-166	28	92	306	161	225	-211	-117	-53	-73	-9	80	269	-262	193	-218	-154	60	124	-21	173	262	-299	-110	25
25	55	119	213	-223	-159	-304	-90	-26	168	257	112	301	-260	-171	23	-122	-58	156	220	-191	264	-267	-78	11	75	25
25	-212	-148	41	130	194	174	243	-293	-104	-15	-185	29	98	312	-249	231	-205	-116	-47	142	-3	86	275	-286	-67	25
25	116	205	-231	-137	52	-93	-29	185	249	-307	298	-238	-174	15	104	-41	153	217	-194	-130	-275	-86	8	72	286	25
25	-156	63	127	191	-220	260	-301	-107	-18	171	26	90	304	-252	-163	-208	-119	-55	159	228	83	272	-264	-75	-11	25
25	202	-234	-145	44	138	-32	182	246	-290	-101	-246	-177	37	101	290	145	234	-197	-133	-44	-64	0	64	283	-278	25
25	-113	-49	140	229	-202	278	-283	-69	-5	84	39	133	197	-214	-150	-295	-106	-12	177	241	96	310	-251	-182	32	25
25	215	-196	-127	-38	151	6	70	284	-272	-83	-228	-139	50	114	208	188	252	-309	-95	-31	-176	18	107	296	-240	25
25	-52	162	226	-210	-121	-266	-72	-8	81	270	125	189	-217	-153	61	-109	-20	169	263	-298	307	-254	-165	24	93	25
25	-199	-135	-46	148	237	67	281	-280	-66	3	-142	47	136	200	-236	244	-287	-98	-34	180	35	99	293	-243	-179	25
25	154	223	-188	-124	-60	-80	9	78	267	-269	211	-225	-161	58	122	-23	166	255	-306	-87	-257	-168	21	110	299	25
25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

It is **pandiagonal bimagic square**. Blocks of order 5 are also **pandiagonal equal sums magic squares**. In this case the **bimagic sum** is $Sb_{25 \times 25} := 813825$.

mgc																								25	
-2	3	2	-4	6	14	-12	32	-30	49	-47	-71	73	108	-106	-114	116	172	-170	-201	203	-240	242	-265	267	25
5	1	-3	-6	8	-20	22	26	-24	48	-46	-60	62	106	-104	131	-129	-145	147	220	-218	263	-261	-269	271	25
0	-1	4	11	-9	-23	25	-37	39	45	-43	-65	67	113	-111	141	-139	-150	152	208	-206	-220	222	-267	269	25
13	12	-8	-5	-7	20	-18	-32	34	44	-42	-68	70	-94	96	-125	127	-159	161	-193	195	257	-255	-271	273	25
-11	-10	10	9	7	16	-14	-36	38	50	-48	76	-74	-97	99	136	-134	168	-166	207	-205	254	-252	-273	275	25
-22	19	18	-19	-21	15	17	-35	37	-57	59	-61	63	109	-107	-121	123	-162	164	-180	182	261	-259	-275	277	25
24	-17	-16	21	23	-15	-13	31	-29	-52	54	79	-77	112	-110	145	-143	-146	148	204	-202	-232	234	-277	279	25
41	35	-27	40	-26	-34	-28	33	-25	-58	60	75	-73	-95	97	-115	117	165	-163	217	-215	-238	240	-279	281	25
-39	-33	29	-38	28	36	30	27	-31	-54	56	78	-76	-102	104	139	-137	167	-165	-186	188	249	-247	-281	283	25
43	-49	-56	-55	53	-53	42	-59	47	46	52	77	-75	110	-108	-118	120	-144	146	-182	184	-241	243	-283	285	25
-41	51	58	57	-51	55	-40	61	-45	-50	-44	-63	65	-90	92	134	-132	-160	162	-200	202	260	-258	-285	287	25
74	84	82	81	-67	-69	-70	-62	83	-66	85	-64	-78	-93	95	-117	119	166	-164	201	-199	-221	223	-287	289	25
-72	-82	-80	-79	69	71	72	64	-81	68	-83	80	66	-88	90	135	-133	-147	149	-204	206	-237	239	293	-291	25
-101	87	-105	-103	-100	-109	94	88	-99	91	93	-96	89	100	86	133	-131	171	-169	-197	199	244	-242	295	-293	25
103	-85	107	105	102	111	-92	-86	101	-89	-91	98	-87	-84	-98	-127	129	-152	154	-189	191	250	-248	297	-295	25
-113	125	144	143	-122	140	138	137	-126	-124	-116	-119	-120	-130	142	-112	130	178	-176	216	-214	252	-250	299	-297	25
115	-123	-142	-141	124	-138	-136	-135	128	126	118	121	122	132	-140	-128	114	173	-171	-183	185	-223	225	301	-299	25
-153	176	-154	-161	180	-156	175	179	-149	-155	177	-148	170	-151	-158	-167	174	181	159	219	-217	248	-246	303	-301	25
155	-174	156	163	-178	158	-173	-177	151	157	-175	150	-168	153	160	169	-172	-157	-179	218	-216	-239	241	305	-303	25
189	187	183	190	-207	-211	193	-210	196	-209	194	186	-203	198	192	-212	-208	-213	200	-195	-219	-236	238	307	-305	25
-187	-185	-181	-188	209	213	-191	212	-194	211	-192	-184	205	-196	-190	214	210	215	-198	221	197	-222	224	309	-307	25
-263	237	-254	-251	226	235	227	-257	-253	229	245	233	246	231	228	-249	-256	-245	236	-260	230	-230	-262	311	-309	25
265	-235	256	253	-224	-233	-225	259	255	-227	-243	-231	-244	-229	-226	251	258	247	-234	262	-228	264	232	313	-311	25
286	268	270	272	274	276	278	280	282	284	266	-289	-290	-292	-294	-296	-298	-300	-302	-304	-306	-308	-310	290	288	25
-284	-266	-268	-270	-272	-274	-276	-278	-280	-282	-264	291	292	294	296	298	300	302	304	306	308	310	312	-286	-288	25
25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

It is **cornered** magic square

mgc																								25	
-271	299	-287	222	-257	-277	236	268	-264	-288	-289	227	-299	241	-226	287	256	225	238	286	-302	230	-232	-260	262	25
273	-297	289	-220	259	279	-234	-266	266	290	291	-225	301	-239	228	-285	-254	-223	-236	-284	304	-228	234	-258	260	25
-263	265	-215	148	-171	146	-204	-217	-188	208	171	200	218	-207	153	-153	156	161	-208	198	-177	-155	157	293	-291	25
-255	257	217	-146	173	-144	206	219	190	-206	-169	-198	-216	209	-151	155	-154	-159	210	-196	179	-166	168	243	-241	25
-230	232	-180	182	141	145	-92	-112	100	88	-111	143	-129	-94	137	-87	-104	118	-128	-95	97	-195	197	306	-304	25
237	-235	-192	194	-139	-143	94	114	-98	-86	113	-141	131	96	-135	89	106	-116	130	-93	95	175	-173	-283	285	25
233	-231	-199	201	133	-131	49	52	76	-82	-72	-53	77	-62	46	-70	50	61	-59	91	-89	-165	167	277	-275	25
-247	249	191	-189	99	-97	-47	-50	-74	84	74	55	-75	64	-44	72	-48	63	-61	117	-115	207	-205	-242	244	25
-224	226	-164	166	101	-99	56	-54	-33	-17	-25	17	18	16	31	29	-27	-58	60	-107	109	-211	213	-229	231	25
245	-243	-162	164	107	-105	-79	81	35	19	27	-15	-16	-14	-29	28	-26	-64	66	-127	129	-175	177	282	-280	25
-238	240	-183	185	-140	142	-67	69	24	-22	4	-9	8	0	2	25	-23	54	-52	139	-137	195	-193	310	-308	25
-261	263	221	-219	115	-113	73	-71	41	-39	-2	11	-6	-4	6	-32	34	48	-46	-122	124	212	-210	239	-237	25
313	-311	189	-187	-85	87	-81	83	-31	33	-11	13	1	7	-5	15	-13	58	-56	125	-123	-178	180	-245	247	25
-272	274	-161	163	90	-88	-42	44	20	-18	5	-3	10	-10	3	-20	22	57	-55	112	-110	-179	181	-268	270	25
-303	305	-149	151	-109	111	-40	42	26	-24	9	-7	-8	12	-1	-38	40	-60	62	-118	120	183	-181	-256	258	25
-251	253	170	-168	-125	127	82	-80	-37	39	23	37	36	-30	-19	-12	-28	-83	85	-84	86	192	-190	-249	251	25
272	-270	-156	158	-100	102	-49	51	-36	38	-21	-35	-34	32	21	14	30	-65	67	144	-142	-145	147	-227	229	25
298	-296	203	-201	110	-108	80	-78	-73	59	43	65	45	79	47	-68	-51	-66	-69	136	-134	160	-158	-293	295	25
311	-309	154	-152	93	-91	78	-76	75	-57	-41	-63	-43	-77	-45	70	53	68	71	-103	105	211	-209	309	-307	25
284	-282	-172	174	-136	138	121	-133	123	-117	-114	103	132	-124	-132	-120	92	98	-126	108	104	220	-218	261	-259	25
-273	275	188	-186	-138	140	-119	135	-121	119	116	-101	-130	126	134	122	-90	-96	128	-106	-102	-167	169	-222	224	25
-246	248	205	-203	196	215	-212	-174	162	-184	-148	-191	184	-147	-157	204	172	202	-163	-150	199	187	-176	281	-279	25
307	-305	216	-214	-194	-213	214	176	-160	186	150	193	-182	149	159	-202	-170	-200	165	152	-197	-185	178	254	-252	25
294	-292	-281	271	223	-253	267	269	-306	-240	278	235	252	-262	-310	-298	302	250	-295	280	246	-286	-301	276	-294	25
292	-290	283	-269	-221	255	-265	-267	308	242	-276	-233	-250	264	312	300	-300	-248	297	-278	-244	288	303	-274	296	25
25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

It is **double-digits bordered** magic square. Except the internal block of order 5 its is constructed based on equal width magic rectangles. We can call it as **almost striped** magic square.

27 Magic Squares with Magic Sum 2025

27.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Below is a magic square of order 3 with magic sum 2025. It is constructed with **sequential entries** from 671 to 679, i.e., $\{671, 672, \dots, 678, 679\}$.

3x3	mgc			2025
	674	679	672	2025
	673	675	677	2025
	678	671	676	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025

27.2 Magic Squares of Order 5

Below are three magic squares of order 5 with magic sum 2025. It is constructed with **sequential entries** from 393 to 417, i.e., {393, 394, ..., 416, 417}.

	pan	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025
2025	393	399	405	411	417	2025	
2025	410	416	397	398	404	2025	
2025	402	403	409	415	396	2025	
2025	414	395	401	407	408	2025	
	406	412	413	394	400	2025	
5x5	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

						2025
	414	417	397	399	398	2025
	394	404	409	402	416	2025
	395	403	405	407	415	2025
	410	408	401	406	400	2025
	412	393	413	411	396	2025
5x5	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

					2025	
	408	403	404	415	395	2025
	401	405	409	417	393	2025
	406	407	402	399	411	2025
	397	398	414	400	416	2025
	413	412	396	394	410	2025
5x5	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

First one is **pandiagonal** magic square. The second one is **bordered** magic square, and the third one is **cornered** magic square.

27.3 Magic Squares of Order 6

Below are 6 magic squares of order 6 with magic sum 2025. These are constructed with **sequential entries** from 320 to 355, i.e., {320, 321, ..., 354, 355}.

6x6	mgc		2025
		320 354 353 352 321 325	2025
		349 327 347 328 330 344	2025
		343 342 334 335 339 332	2025
		337 333 340 341 336 338	2025
		326 345 329 346 348 331	2025
		350 324 322 323 351 355	2025
©IJT		339 339 339 339 339 339	2025

6x6	mgc		2025
		325 349 322 355 323 351	2025
		354 336 341 330 343 321	2025
		348 331 342 337 340 327	2025
		346 345 332 339 334 329	2025
		328 338 335 344 333 347	2025
		324 326 353 320 352 350	2025
©IJT		339 339 339 339 339 339	2025

The first one is traditional magic square. The second one is **bordered** magic square. The internal block is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

6x6	mgc		2025
		336 341 330 343 348 327	2025
		331 342 337 340 346 329	2025
		345 332 339 334 354 321	2025
		338 335 344 333 328 347	2025
		323 322 355 349 325 351	2025
		352 353 320 326 324 350	2025
©IJT		339 339 339 339 339 339	2025

6x6	mgc		2025
		343 336 341 335 333 337	2025
		326 350 324 352 353 320	2025
		348 346 328 331 345 327	2025
		321 329 347 344 330 354	2025
		355 325 351 323 322 349	2025
		332 339 334 340 342 338	2025
©IJT		339 339 339 339 339 339	2025

The first magic square is **cornered** magic square. The second one is composed internal block of **bordered magic rectangle**.

6x6	mgc		2025
		330 347 329 344 322 353	2025
		345 328 346 331 355 320	2025
		325 348 351 326 321 354	2025
		350 327 324 349 352 323	2025
		340 332 339 338 334 342	2025
		335 343 336 337 341 333	2025
©IJT		339 339 339 339 339 339	2025

6x6	mgc		2025
		330 345 325 350 322 353	2025
		347 328 348 327 355 320	2025
		329 346 351 324 321 354	2025
		344 331 326 349 352 323	2025
		340 332 339 338 334 342	2025
		335 343 336 337 341 333	2025
©IJT		339 339 339 339 339 339	2025

These two magic squares are **striped** magic square with equal width magic rectangles. The first one is **cornered-type striped** magic square.

27.4 Magic Squares of Order 9

Below are 4 magic squares of order 9 with magic sum 2025. These are constructed with **sequential entries** from 185 to 265, i.e., $\{185, 186, \dots, 264, 265\}$.

10x10	mgc										2025	
		243	238	168	236	170	166	156	250	154	244	2025
		165	178	172	232	234	221	183	223	177	240	2025
		241	175	216	214	187	220	188	190	230	164	2025
		163	176	186	201	206	195	208	219	229	242	2025
		248	181	192	196	207	202	205	213	224	157	2025
		153	231	194	210	197	204	199	211	174	252	2025
		245	226	212	203	200	209	198	193	179	160	2025
		159	225	215	191	218	185	217	189	180	246	2025
		247	228	233	173	171	184	222	182	227	158	2025
		161	167	237	169	235	239	249	155	251	162	2025
		2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

10x10	mgc										2025	
		243	238	168	236	170	166	156	250	154	244	2025
		165	199	210	171	230	191	218	179	222	240	2025
		241	174	227	202	207	182	219	194	215	164	2025
		163	234	175	206	195	226	183	214	187	242	2025
		248	203	198	231	178	211	190	223	186	157	2025
		153	200	209	172	229	192	217	180	221	252	2025
		245	173	228	201	208	181	220	193	216	160	2025
		159	233	176	205	196	225	184	213	188	246	2025
		247	204	197	232	177	212	189	224	185	158	2025
		161	167	237	169	235	239	249	155	251	162	2025
		2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

The first magic square is **pandiagonal** magic square with equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. The second magic square is **single digit bordered** magic square.

10x10	mgc										2025	
		156	249	246	159	200	205	173	232	177	228	2025
		250	155	160	245	211	194	231	174	227	178	2025
		153	252	247	158	195	210	230	175	226	179	2025
		251	154	157	248	203	202	176	229	180	225	2025
		165	239	238	168	209	196	185	219	218	188	2025
		240	166	167	237	193	212	220	186	187	217	2025
		169	236	161	244	206	199	184	221	214	191	2025
		235	170	243	162	207	198	222	183	192	213	2025
		234	171	242	163	204	201	181	224	215	190	2025
		172	233	164	241	197	208	223	182	189	216	2025
		2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

10x10	mgc										2025	
		155	153	251	249	248	158	246	160	161	244	2025
		250	252	154	156	157	247	159	245	163	242	2025
		177	228	195	210	190	215	187	218	243	162	2025
		227	178	212	193	213	192	220	185	241	164	2025
		179	226	194	211	216	189	186	219	240	165	2025
		225	180	209	196	191	214	217	188	166	239	2025
		224	181	205	197	204	203	199	207	238	167	2025
		222	183	200	208	201	202	206	198	168	237	2025
		184	221	169	235	171	233	176	174	230	232	2025
		182	223	236	170	234	172	229	231	175	173	2025
		2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

The first magic square is **cornered** magic square. The second one is **double digits bordered** magic square.

27.5 Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are 6 magic squares of order 10 with magic sum 2025. These are constructed with **sequential entries** from 153 to 252, i.e., $\{153, 154, \dots, 251, 252\}$.

10x10	mgc											2025
		243	238	168	236	170	166	156	250	154	244	2025
		165	178	172	232	234	221	183	223	177	240	2025
		241	175	216	214	187	220	188	190	230	164	2025
		163	176	186	201	206	195	208	219	229	242	2025
		248	181	192	196	207	202	205	213	224	157	2025
		153	231	194	210	197	204	199	211	174	252	2025
		245	226	212	203	200	209	198	193	179	160	2025
		159	225	215	191	218	185	217	189	180	246	2025
		247	228	233	173	171	184	222	182	227	158	2025
		161	167	237	169	235	239	249	155	251	162	2025
		2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

10x10	mgc											2025
		243	238	168	236	170	166	156	250	154	244	2025
		165	199	210	171	230	191	218	179	222	240	2025
		241	174	227	202	207	182	219	194	215	164	2025
		163	234	175	206	195	226	183	214	187	242	2025
		248	203	198	231	178	211	190	223	186	157	2025
		153	200	209	172	229	192	217	180	221	252	2025
		245	173	228	201	208	181	220	193	216	160	2025
		159	233	176	205	196	225	184	213	188	246	2025
		247	204	197	232	177	212	189	224	185	158	2025
		161	167	237	169	235	239	249	155	251	162	2025
		2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

First magic square is bordered magic square. The second one is **block-bordered** magic square. The internal block is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8. It is composed of 4 equal sums magic squares of order 4.

10x10	mgc										2025
	156	249	246	159	200	205	173	232	177	228	2025
	250	155	160	245	211	194	231	174	227	178	2025
	153	252	247	158	195	210	230	175	226	179	2025
	251	154	157	248	203	202	176	229	180	225	2025
	165	239	238	168	209	196	185	219	218	188	2025
	240	166	167	237	193	212	220	186	187	217	2025
	169	236	161	244	206	199	184	221	214	191	2025
	235	170	243	162	207	198	222	183	192	213	2025
	234	171	242	163	204	201	181	224	215	190	2025
	172	233	164	241	197	208	223	182	189	216	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

10x10	mgc										2025
	155	153	251	249	248	158	246	160	161	244	2025
	250	252	154	156	157	247	159	245	163	242	2025
	177	228	195	210	190	215	187	218	243	162	2025
	227	178	212	193	213	192	220	185	241	164	2025
	179	226	194	211	216	189	186	219	240	165	2025
	225	180	209	196	191	214	217	188	166	239	2025
	224	181	205	197	204	203	199	207	238	167	2025
	222	183	200	208	201	202	206	198	168	237	2025
	184	221	169	235	171	233	176	174	230	232	2025
	182	223	236	170	234	172	229	231	175	173	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

These two magic squares are **striped** magic squares. The second one is **double digits bordered** magic square. The internal block is striped magic square of order 6.

10x10	mgc										2025
	189	215	214	192	185	220	227	178	238	167	2025
	216	190	191	213	219	186	177	228	168	237	2025
	184	222	181	223	218	187	226	179	163	242	2025
	221	183	224	182	188	217	180	225	241	164	2025
	169	174	171	233	230	232	235	176	240	165	2025
	236	231	234	172	175	173	170	229	166	239	2025
	155	249	153	251	248	158	246	160	161	244	2025
	250	156	252	154	157	247	159	245	243	162	2025
	195	211	200	203	197	207	206	204	193	209	2025
	210	194	205	202	208	198	199	201	212	196	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

10x10	mgc										2025
	165	240	245	160	220	185	221	175	190	224	2025
	170	235	247	158	192	213	184	230	215	181	2025
	237	168	157	248	182	223	206	199	174	231	2025
	239	166	159	246	196	209	200	205	210	195	2025
	236	169	242	163	232	173	201	204	211	194	2025
	172	233	162	243	186	219	198	207	226	179	2025
	234	171	244	161	225	180	208	197	212	193	2025
	167	238	164	241	187	218	202	203	188	217	2025
	153	251	250	156	229	214	189	178	177	228	2025
	252	154	155	249	176	191	216	227	222	183	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

These two magic squares are **striped** magic squares. The first one is **cornered-type** magic square.

27.6 Magic Squares of Order 15

Below are four magic squares of order 15 with magic sum 2025. These are constructed with **sequential entries** from 23 to 247, i.e., $\{23, 24, \dots, 246, 247\}$

15x15	pan	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025
2025	208	87	110	209	96	100	210	97	98	211	86	108	212	84	109	2025
2025	102	215	88	111	205	89	112	203	90	101	213	91	99	214	92	2025
2025	95	103	207	85	104	216	83	105	217	93	106	206	94	107	204	2025
2025	58	222	125	59	231	115	60	232	113	61	221	123	62	219	124	2025
2025	117	65	223	126	55	224	127	53	225	116	63	226	114	64	227	2025
2025	230	118	57	220	119	66	218	120	67	228	121	56	229	122	54	2025
2025	28	237	140	29	246	130	30	247	128	31	236	138	32	234	139	2025
2025	132	35	238	141	25	239	142	23	240	131	33	241	129	34	242	2025
2025	245	133	27	235	134	36	233	135	37	243	136	26	244	137	24	2025
2025	178	72	155	179	81	145	180	82	143	181	71	153	182	69	154	2025
2025	147	185	73	156	175	74	157	173	75	146	183	76	144	184	77	2025
2025	80	148	177	70	149	186	68	150	187	78	151	176	79	152	174	2025
2025	193	42	170	194	51	160	195	52	158	196	41	168	197	39	169	2025
2025	162	200	43	171	190	44	172	188	45	161	198	46	159	199	47	2025
	50	163	192	40	164	201	38	165	202	48	166	191	49	167	189	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is **pandiagonal** magic square with equal sum **semi-magic** squares of order 3.

15x15	pan	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025
2025	23	109	133	200	210	25	108	132	201	209	24	107	131	202	211	2025
2025	193	215	30	98	139	192	216	29	100	138	191	217	31	99	137	2025
2025	105	128	199	208	35	104	130	198	207	36	106	129	197	206	37	2025
2025	214	28	110	135	188	213	27	111	134	190	212	26	112	136	189	2025
2025	140	195	203	34	103	141	194	205	33	102	142	196	204	32	101	2025
2025	53	94	118	185	225	55	93	117	186	224	54	92	116	187	226	2025
2025	178	230	60	83	124	177	231	59	85	123	176	232	61	84	122	2025
2025	90	113	184	223	65	89	115	183	222	66	91	114	182	221	67	2025
2025	229	58	95	120	173	228	57	96	119	175	227	56	97	121	174	2025
2025	125	180	218	64	88	126	179	220	63	87	127	181	219	62	86	2025
2025	38	79	148	170	240	40	78	147	171	239	39	77	146	172	241	2025
2025	163	245	45	68	154	162	246	44	70	153	161	247	46	69	152	2025
2025	75	143	169	238	50	74	145	168	237	51	76	144	167	236	52	2025
2025	244	43	80	150	158	243	42	81	149	160	242	41	82	151	159	2025
	155	165	233	49	73	156	164	235	48	72	157	166	234	47	71	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is **pandiagonal** magic square with equal sum **pandiagonal** squares of order 5.

15x15	mgc													2025		
	132	139	134	147	123	149	121	166	104	89	181	74	196	31	239	2025
	137	135	133	146	124	155	115	164	106	86	184	63	207	25	245	2025
	136	131	138	126	144	116	154	101	169	189	81	62	208	30	240	2025
	130	128	145	129	143	111	159	100	170	190	80	206	64	227	43	2025
	140	142	125	127	141	114	156	162	108	85	185	72	198	29	241	2025
	112	113	153	150	151	148	118	160	110	84	186	213	57	223	47	2025
	158	157	117	120	119	152	122	168	102	193	77	217	53	235	35	2025
	171	175	109	105	103	173	107	98	174	194	76	212	58	228	42	2025
	99	95	161	165	167	97	163	96	172	93	177	67	203	23	247	2025
	92	82	91	192	187	94	191	88	90	195	183	73	197	225	45	2025
	178	188	179	78	83	176	79	182	180	87	75	218	52	28	242	2025
	202	56	204	205	201	54	209	55	199	60	200	59	51	237	33	2025
	68	214	66	65	69	216	61	215	71	210	70	219	211	32	238	2025
	246	243	233	48	39	234	41	46	236	244	44	40	49	232	50	2025
	24	27	37	222	231	36	229	224	34	26	226	230	221	220	38	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is **cornered** magic square.

15x15	mgc															2025
	42	30	231	233	44	208	64	247	48	69	239	244	56	216	54	2025
	228	240	39	37	226	62	206	23	222	201	31	26	214	50	220	2025
	197	73	107	106	103	194	96	83	166	190	170	176	94	205	65	2025
	215	55	163	164	167	76	174	187	104	80	100	185	85	237	33	2025
	202	68	110	160	150	158	128	126	113	154	116	109	161	234	36	2025
	57	213	99	171	120	112	142	144	157	148	122	105	165	241	29	2025
	40	230	79	191	124	146	136	131	138	111	159	88	182	74	196	2025
	41	229	98	172	118	152	137	135	133	143	127	97	173	46	224	2025
	28	242	82	188	129	141	132	139	134	119	151	181	89	71	199	2025
	246	24	195	75	149	121	147	156	130	125	117	193	77	35	235	2025
	47	223	177	93	155	115	123	114	140	145	153	81	189	43	227	2025
	198	72	192	78	91	84	184	162	175	90	92	168	169	58	212	2025
	200	70	183	87	179	186	86	108	95	180	178	102	101	245	25	2025
	59	211	217	38	32	52	204	210	203	27	207	236	219	49	61	2025
	225	45	53	232	238	218	66	60	67	243	63	34	51	221	209	2025
	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is **double-digits bordered** magic square.

27.7 Magic Squares of Order 18

Below are four magic squares of order 18 with magic sum 2025. These are constructed with **sequential entries**: $\{-49, -48, \dots, 273, 274\}$

18x18	mgc																		2025	
	-31	-11	-48	143	127	162	196	212	177	250	230	267	89	109	72	28	8	45	2025	
	-47	-30	-13	163	144	125	176	195	214	266	249	232	73	90	107	44	27	10	2025	
	-12	-49	-29	126	161	145	213	178	194	231	268	248	108	71	91	9	46	26	2025	
	197	217	180	23	7	42	251	235	270	82	98	63	137	121	156	-19	1	-36	2025	
	181	198	215	43	24	5	271	252	233	62	81	100	157	138	119	-35	-18	-1	2025	
	216	179	199	6	41	25	234	269	253	99	64	80	120	155	139	0	-37	-17	2025	
	40	20	57	-14	2	-33	77	97	60	191	211	174	239	223	258	142	122	159	2025	
	56	39	22	-34	-15	4	61	78	95	175	192	209	259	240	221	158	141	124	2025	
	21	58	38	3	-32	-16	96	59	79	210	173	193	222	257	241	123	160	140	2025	
	244	224	261	88	104	69	-20	-4	-39	148	128	165	34	14	51	185	205	168	2025	
	260	243	226	68	87	106	-40	-21	-2	164	147	130	50	33	16	169	186	203	2025	
	225	262	242	105	70	86	-3	-38	-22	129	166	146	15	52	32	204	167	187	2025	
	131	115	150	245	229	264	35	19	54	-25	-5	-42	202	218	183	83	103	66	2025	
	151	132	113	265	246	227	55	36	17	-41	-24	-7	182	201	220	67	84	101	2025	
	114	149	133	228	263	247	18	53	37	-6	-43	-23	219	184	200	102	65	85	2025	
	94	110	75	190	206	171	136	116	153	29	13	48	-26	-10	-45	256	236	273	2025	
	74	93	112	170	189	208	152	135	118	49	30	11	-46	-27	-8	272	255	238	2025	
	111	76	92	207	172	188	117	154	134	12	47	31	-9	-44	-28	237	274	254	2025	
©IJT	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is constructed with different sums magic squares of order 3.

18x18	mgc																		2025
	-49	257	256	239	-32	4	-48	258	255	240	-33	3	-47	259	254	241	-34	2	2025
	220	22	202	23	41	167	219	21	201	24	42	168	218	20	200	25	43	169	2025
	166	149	77	94	130	59	165	150	78	93	129	60	164	151	79	92	128	61	2025
	112	76	131	148	95	113	111	75	132	147	96	114	110	74	133	146	97	115	2025
	5	184	40	185	203	58	6	183	39	186	204	57	7	182	38	187	205	56	2025
	221	-13	-31	-14	238	274	222	-12	-30	-15	237	273	223	-11	-29	-16	236	272	2025
	-46	260	253	242	-35	1	-45	261	252	243	-36	0	-44	262	251	244	-37	-1	2025
	217	19	199	26	44	170	216	18	198	27	45	171	215	17	197	28	46	172	2025
	163	152	80	91	127	62	162	153	81	90	126	63	161	154	82	89	125	64	2025
	109	73	134	145	98	116	108	72	135	144	99	117	107	71	136	143	100	118	2025
	8	181	37	188	206	55	9	180	36	189	207	54	10	179	35	190	208	53	2025
	224	-10	-28	-17	235	271	225	-9	-27	-18	234	270	226	-8	-26	-19	233	269	2025
	-43	263	250	245	-38	-2	-42	264	249	246	-39	-3	-41	265	248	247	-40	-4	2025
	214	16	196	29	47	173	213	15	195	30	48	174	212	14	194	31	49	175	2025
	160	155	83	88	124	65	159	156	84	87	123	66	158	157	85	86	122	67	2025
	106	70	137	142	101	119	105	69	138	141	102	120	104	68	139	140	103	121	2025
	11	178	34	191	209	52	12	177	33	192	210	51	13	176	32	193	211	50	2025
	227	-7	-25	-20	232	268	228	-6	-24	-21	231	267	229	-5	-23	-22	230	266	2025
©IJT	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is constructed with equal sums magic squares of order 6.

18x18	mgc																	2025		
	111	116	105	118	128	97	131	94	154	71	176	49	35	190	11	214	-22	247	2025	
	106	117	112	115	127	98	92	133	157	68	171	54	16	209	231	-6	262	-37	2025	
	120	107	114	109	96	129	90	135	76	149	169	56	21	204	220	5	-16	241	2025	
	113	110	119	108	100	125	85	140	65	160	55	170	205	20	-4	229	-39	264	2025	
	103	95	126	104	123	124	87	138	75	150	163	62	33	192	212	13	-47	272	2025	
	122	130	99	121	101	102	136	89	162	63	58	167	24	201	14	211	-17	242	2025	
	82	139	81	93	141	134	142	88	64	161	173	52	202	23	232	-7	246	-21	2025	
	143	86	144	132	84	91	137	83	152	73	59	166	31	194	223	2	-32	257	2025	
	77	67	153	147	145	159	155	79	69	74	183	42	197	28	236	-11	258	-33	2025	
	148	158	72	78	80	66	70	146	151	156	48	177	195	30	-15	240	255	-30	2025	
	61	41	174	57	165	44	46	178	182	172	50	180	187	38	-12	237	252	-27	2025	
	164	184	51	168	60	181	179	47	43	53	45	175	32	193	213	12	268	-43	2025	
	40	189	198	17	18	196	200	199	39	210	22	37	191	19	-10	235	-31	256	2025	
	185	36	27	208	207	29	25	26	186	15	203	188	206	34	9	216	254	-29	2025	
	-5	-14	238	-3	-9	4	217	226	3	224	10	225	227	6	233	218	261	-36	2025	
	230	239	-13	228	234	221	8	-1	222	1	215	0	-2	219	7	-8	-49	274	2025	
	-28	-34	269	-45	-26	-41	273	250	-42	-18	271	244	263	260	-24	-40	245	248	2025	
	253	259	-44	270	251	266	-48	-25	267	243	-46	-19	-38	-35	249	265	-23	-20	2025	
©IJT	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is cornered magic square. If we replace the internal block of order 6 by **striped** magic square of order 6, then this magic square becomes as **striped** magic square.

18x18	mgc																	2025	
	-49	-47	273	271	270	-44	268	-42	-41	265	-39	263	262	-36	260	-34	-33	258	2025
	274	272	-48	-46	-45	269	-43	267	266	-40	264	-38	-37	261	-35	259	-31	256	2025
	-1	226	15	17	209	207	206	205	21	22	23	201	25	199	27	198	257	-32	2025
	225	0	210	208	16	18	19	20	204	203	202	24	200	26	29	196	255	-30	2025
	1	224	51	174	65	63	161	159	158	68	156	70	71	154	197	28	254	-29	2025
	223	2	173	52	160	162	64	66	67	157	69	155	73	152	195	30	-28	253	2025
	222	3	53	172	87	138	95	129	128	127	96	100	153	72	194	31	252	-27	2025
	4	221	171	54	137	88	124	102	122	103	105	119	151	74	193	32	-26	251	2025
	220	5	170	55	89	136	118	117	109	110	114	107	150	75	33	192	-25	250	2025
	6	219	169	56	135	90	112	108	115	116	111	113	76	149	34	191	249	-24	2025
	7	218	57	168	134	91	101	120	104	121	123	106	148	77	35	190	-23	248	2025
	217	8	58	167	132	93	125	99	97	98	126	130	78	147	189	36	247	-22	2025
	9	216	59	166	94	131	79	145	81	143	86	84	140	142	37	188	246	-21	2025
	215	10	61	164	92	133	146	80	144	82	139	141	85	83	187	38	-20	245	2025
	214	11	165	60	39	185	41	183	182	181	45	46	47	49	177	175	244	-19	2025
	212	13	163	62	186	40	184	42	43	44	180	179	178	176	48	50	-18	243	2025
	14	211	-17	241	-15	239	238	-12	236	-10	-9	233	-7	231	230	228	-2	-4	2025
	12	213	242	-16	240	-14	-13	237	-11	235	234	-8	232	-6	-5	-3	227	229	2025
©IJT	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is double-digits bordered magic square.

27.8 Magic Squares of Order 25

Below are four magic squares of order 25 with magic sum 2025. These are constructed with **sequential entries**: $\{-231, -230, \dots, 392, 393\}$

pan	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	
2025	-231	-12	52	266	330	185	374	-157	-93	96	-49	40	229	298	-113	367	-194	-5	84	153	133	197	286	-150	-61	2025
2025	252	341	-220	-31	63	-82	107	171	385	-176	304	-127	-38	26	240	70	159	353	-183	6	-139	-75	139	208	272	2025
2025	-20	44	263	327	-209	371	-165	-101	118	182	37	226	315	-121	-52	-197	17	81	145	359	214	283	-153	-64	125	2025
2025	338	-223	-9	55	244	99	193	382	-179	-90	-110	-46	23	237	301	156	345	-191	3	92	-78	136	200	289	-142	2025
2025	66	255	319	-212	-23	-168	-104	110	174	393	223	312	-124	-35	29	9	78	167	356	-205	275	-136	-67	122	211	2025
2025	351	-185	4	73	162	142	206	270	-141	-72	-217	-28	61	250	339	169	388	-173	-84	105	-40	24	243	307	-129	2025
2025	79	148	362	-199	15	-155	-66	128	217	281	261	325	-211	-17	47	-98	116	180	369	-162	318	-118	-54	35	224	2025
2025	-188	1	90	154	348	203	292	-144	-80	134	-11	58	247	336	-225	380	-181	-87	102	191	21	235	299	-107	-43	2025
2025	165	354	-202	12	76	-69	120	209	278	-133	322	-214	-25	64	258	113	177	391	-170	-106	-126	-32	32	221	310	2025
2025	-2	87	151	365	-196	284	-147	-58	131	195	50	264	333	-228	-14	-159	-95	94	188	377	232	296	-115	-51	43	2025
2025	183	372	-164	-100	114	-56	38	227	316	-120	360	-201	18	82	146	126	215	279	-152	-63	-208	-19	45	259	328	2025
2025	-89	100	189	383	-178	302	-109	-45	19	238	93	157	346	-190	-1	-146	-77	137	201	290	245	334	-222	-8	56	2025
2025	389	-167	-103	111	175	30	219	313	-123	-34	-204	10	74	168	357	212	276	-135	-71	123	-22	67	256	320	-216	2025
2025	97	186	375	-161	-92	-112	-48	41	230	294	149	368	-193	-4	85	-60	129	198	287	-149	331	-230	-16	53	267	2025
2025	-175	-86	108	172	386	241	305	-131	-37	27	7	71	160	349	-182	273	-138	-74	140	204	59	253	342	-219	-30	2025
2025	135	199	293	-143	-79	-224	-10	54	248	337	192	381	-180	-91	103	-42	22	236	300	-111	344	-187	2	91	155	2025
2025	-132	-68	121	210	274	254	323	-213	-24	65	-105	109	178	392	-169	311	-125	-36	33	222	77	166	355	-206	13	2025
2025	196	285	-151	-57	132	-13	51	265	329	-227	378	-158	-94	95	184	39	233	297	-114	-50	-195	-6	88	152	366	2025
2025	-76	143	207	271	-140	340	-221	-27	62	251	106	170	384	-172	-83	-128	-39	25	239	308	163	352	-184	5	69	2025
2025	282	-154	-65	124	218	48	262	326	-210	-21	-166	-97	117	181	370	225	314	-117	-53	36	16	80	144	363	-198	2025
2025	-33	31	220	309	-122	358	-203	11	75	164	119	213	277	-134	-70	-215	-26	68	257	321	176	390	-171	-102	112	2025
2025	295	-116	-47	42	231	86	150	364	-192	-3	-148	-59	130	194	288	268	332	-229	-15	49	-96	98	187	376	-160	2025
2025	28	242	306	-130	-41	-186	8	72	161	350	205	269	-137	-73	141	-29	60	249	343	-218	387	-174	-85	104	173	2025
2025	-119	-55	34	228	317	147	361	-200	14	83	-62	127	216	280	-156	324	-207	-18	46	260	115	179	373	-163	-99	2025
2025	234	303	-108	-44	20	0	89	158	347	-189	291	-145	-81	138	202	57	246	335	-226	-7	-177	-88	101	190	379	2025
2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is **pandiagonal bimagic** square. Blocks of order 5 are also **pandiagonal** equal sums magic squares. In this case the **bimagic** sum is $Sb_{25 \times 25} := 977825$.

mgc																								2025	
78	83	82	76	86	94	68	112	50	129	33	9	153	188	-26	-34	196	252	-90	-121	283	-160	322	-185	347	2025
85	81	77	74	88	60	102	106	56	128	34	20	142	186	-24	211	-49	-65	227	300	-138	343	-181	-189	351	2025
80	79	84	91	71	57	105	43	119	125	37	15	147	193	-31	221	-59	-70	232	288	-126	-140	302	-187	349	2025
93	92	72	75	73	100	62	48	114	124	38	12	150	-14	176	-45	207	-79	241	-113	275	337	-175	-191	353	2025
69	70	90	89	87	96	66	44	118	130	32	156	6	-17	179	216	-54	248	-86	287	-125	334	-172	-193	355	2025
58	99	98	61	59	95	97	45	117	23	139	19	143	189	-27	-41	203	-82	244	-100	262	341	-179	-195	357	2025
104	63	64	101	103	65	67	111	51	28	134	159	3	192	-30	225	-63	-66	228	284	-122	-152	314	-197	359	2025
121	115	53	120	54	46	52	113	55	22	140	155	7	-15	177	-35	197	245	-83	297	-135	-158	320	-199	361	2025
41	47	109	42	108	116	110	107	49	26	136	158	4	-22	184	219	-57	247	-85	-106	268	329	-167	-201	363	2025
123	31	24	25	133	27	122	21	127	126	132	157	5	190	-28	-38	200	-64	226	-102	264	-161	323	-203	365	2025
39	131	138	137	29	135	40	141	35	30	36	17	145	-10	172	214	-52	-80	242	-120	282	340	-178	-205	367	2025
154	164	162	161	13	11	10	18	163	14	165	16	2	-13	175	-37	199	246	-84	281	-119	-141	303	-207	369	2025
8	-2	0	1	149	151	152	144	-1	148	-3	160	146	-8	170	215	-53	-67	229	-124	286	-157	319	373	-211	2025
-21	167	-25	-23	-20	-29	174	168	-19	171	173	-16	169	180	166	213	-51	251	-89	-117	279	324	-162	375	-213	2025
183	-5	187	185	182	191	-12	-6	181	-9	-11	178	-7	-4	-18	-47	209	-72	234	-109	271	330	-168	377	-215	2025
-33	205	224	223	-42	220	218	217	-46	-44	-36	-39	-40	-50	222	-32	210	258	-96	296	-134	332	-170	379	-217	2025
195	-43	-62	-61	204	-58	-56	-55	208	206	198	201	202	212	-60	-48	194	253	-91	-103	265	-143	305	381	-219	2025
-73	256	-74	-81	260	-76	255	259	-69	-75	257	-68	250	-71	-78	-87	254	261	239	299	-137	328	-166	383	-221	2025
235	-94	236	243	-98	238	-93	-97	231	237	-95	230	-88	233	240	249	-92	-77	-99	298	-136	-159	321	385	-223	2025
269	267	263	270	-127	-131	273	-130	276	-129	274	266	-123	278	272	-132	-128	-133	280	-115	-139	-156	318	387	-225	2025
-107	-105	-101	-108	289	293	-111	292	-114	291	-112	-104	285	-116	-110	294	290	295	-118	301	277	-142	304	389	-227	2025
-183	317	-174	-171	306	315	307	-177	-173	309	325	313	326	311	308	-169	-176	-165	316	-180	310	-150	-182	391	-229	2025
345	-155	336	333	-144	-153	-145	339	335	-147	-163	-151	-164	-149	-146	331	338	327	-154	342	-148	344	312	393	-231	2025
366	348	350	352	354	356	358	360	362	364	346	-209	-210	-212	-214	-216	-218	-220	-222	-224	-226	-228	-230	370	368	2025
-204	-186	-188	-190	-192	-194	-196	-198	-200	-202	-184	371	372	374	376	378	380	382	384	386	388	390	392	-206	-208	2025
2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is **cornered** magic square

mgc																								2025	
-191	379	-207	302	-177	-197	316	348	-184	-208	-209	307	-219	321	-146	367	336	305	318	366	-222	310	-152	-180	342	2025
353	-217	369	-140	339	359	-154	-186	346	370	371	-145	381	-159	308	-205	-174	-143	-156	-204	384	-148	314	-178	340	2025
-183	345	-135	228	-91	226	-124	-137	-108	288	251	280	298	-127	233	-73	236	241	-128	278	-97	-75	237	373	-211	2025
-175	337	297	-66	253	-64	286	299	270	-126	-89	-118	-136	289	-71	235	-74	-79	290	-116	259	-86	248	323	-161	2025
-150	312	-100	262	221	225	-12	-32	180	168	-31	223	-49	-14	217	-7	-24	198	-48	-15	177	-115	277	386	-224	2025
317	-155	-112	274	-59	-63	174	194	-18	-6	193	-61	211	176	-55	169	186	-36	210	-13	175	255	-93	-203	365	2025
313	-151	-119	281	213	-51	129	132	156	-2	8	27	157	18	126	10	130	141	21	171	-9	-85	247	357	-195	2025
-167	329	271	-109	179	-17	33	30	6	164	154	135	5	144	36	152	32	143	19	197	-35	287	-125	-162	324	2025
-144	306	-84	246	181	-19	136	26	47	63	55	97	98	96	111	109	53	22	140	-27	189	-131	293	-149	311	2025
325	-163	-82	244	187	-25	1	161	115	99	107	65	64	66	51	108	54	16	146	-47	209	-95	257	362	-200	2025
-158	320	-103	265	-60	222	13	149	104	58	84	71	88	80	82	105	57	134	28	219	-57	275	-113	390	-228	2025
-181	343	301	-139	195	-33	153	9	121	41	78	91	74	76	86	48	114	128	34	-42	204	292	-130	319	-157	2025
393	-231	269	-107	-5	167	-1	163	49	113	69	93	81	87	75	95	67	138	24	205	-43	-98	260	-165	327	2025
-192	354	-81	243	170	-8	38	124	100	62	85	77	90	70	83	60	102	137	25	192	-30	-99	261	-188	350	2025
-223	385	-69	231	-29	191	40	122	106	56	89	73	72	92	79	42	120	20	142	-38	200	263	-101	-176	338	2025
-171	333	250	-88	-45	207	162	0	43	119	103	117	116	50	61	68	52	-3	165	-4	166	272	-110	-169	331	2025
352	-190	-76	238	-20	182	31	131	44	118	59	45	46	112	101	94	110	15	147	224	-62	-65	227	-147	309	2025
378	-216	283	-121	190	-28	160	2	7	139	123	145	125	159	127	12	29	14	11	216	-54	240	-78	-213	375	2025
391	-229	234	-72	173	-11	158	4	155	23	39	17	37	3	35	150	133	148	151	-23	185	291	-129	389	-227	2025
364	-202	-92	254	-56	218	201	-53	203	-37	-34	183	212	-44	-52	-40	172	178	-46	188	184	300	-138	341	-179	2025
-193	355	268	-106	-58	220	-39	215	-41	199	196	-21	-50	206	214	202	-10	-16	208	-26	-22	-87	249	-142	304	2025
-166	328	285	-123	276	295	-132	-94	242	-104	-68	-111	264	-67	-77	284	252	282	-83	-70	279	267	-96	361	-199	2025
387	-225	296	-134	-114	-133	294	256	-80	266	230	273	-102	229	239	-122	-90	-120	245	232	-117	-105	258	334	-172	2025
374	-212	-201	351	303	-173	347	349	-226	-160	358	315	332	-182	-230	-218	382	330	-215	360	326	-206	-221	356	-214	2025
372	-210	363	-189	-141	335	-185	-187	388	322	-196	-153	-170	344	392	380	-220	-168	377	-198	-164	368	383	-194	376	2025
2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025

It is **double-digits bordered** magic square. Except the internal block order 5, it is constructed with equal width of magic rectangles. We can call it as **almost striped** magic square.

28 Author's Contributions to Magic Squares

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 1. <https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
 2. <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 1. <https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>
 2. <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>

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- [2] **C. Boyer**, Multimagic Squares, <http://www.multimagie.com>.
- [3] **H. White**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BlockSquares.html>
- [4] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares with Magic Sum 2020, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>
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Also see the link: **Inder J. Taneja**, Geometrical, Numerical, and Symmetrical Representations for the Days of 2020 <https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/2020/10/07/geometrical-numerical-and-symmetrical-representations-for-the-days-of-2020/>

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- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, 21 Mathematical Highlights for 2021, **Zenodo**, December 26, 2020, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4394408>.
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- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022, **Zenodo**, December 28, 2021, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807789>.
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● Universal and Upside-down Magic Squares

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